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IMPLEMENTING EVIDENCE-BASED PRACTICES FOR INTERDISCIPLINARY
ROUNDING: PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds for our inpatient team were based on a two-decade old practice of tradition and a belief that the rounds were only conducted because of regulatory requirements. Practices based on tradition resulted in ineffective and inefficient approaches to coordination of care. Shared interprofessional decision-making and patient-centered individualized plans of care were missing from our teams' interdisciplinary patient care rounding process. The team reviewed literature and, based on that evidence, discussed how to redesign the structures and processes of rounding. The team considered 13 evidence-informed processes for patient care rounds, team centered communication strategies, and how to include the patient and family in the interdisciplinary patient care rounding process. A 4-week pilot was conducted to assess and evaluate the proposed changes in the interdisciplinary patient care rounds. Structured observations and appreciative inquiry debriefings were used to obtain feedback during the pilot period. Feedback was incorporated in each subsequent week's interdisciplinary patient care rounds. Eleven of 13 evidence-based practices described in the literature were included in the final implementation of the interdisciplinary patient care rounding process. Team members' roles were defined, a standardized time and location for rounds was determined, and an electronic structured note for patient-centered goal development and documentation were implemented using the "patient story" element in the electronic medical record. Conducting interdisciplinary patient care rounds in a conference room

setting instead of the previous hallway rounds led to a decrease in interruptions and a reduction in time wasting activities.

Leadership style, including team involvement in the development of the new rounding process and frequent team input during the pilot phase were supportive for maintaining team momentum in change implementation. Real-time adjustments based on team feedback led to enhanced team involvement and acceptance of the new rounding process. A reduction of interruptions and distractions with no change in rounding time may have indicated a more patient-centered focus of rounding discussions.

Recommendations for the future include actual presence of the patient and family during interdisciplinary patient care rounds to further enhance patient-and-family centered care and team training using an interprofessional communication skills lab to enhance respect between various professionals and invite additional, active participation from all team members. Data collection is in process for outcome evaluation of the new interdisciplinary patient care rounds process and the project on clinical outcomes, such as length of stay, as well as on patient satisfaction, care provider satisfaction outcome measures, and work efficiency outcomes.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	viii
LIST OF FIGURES.....	ix
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	x
BACKGROUND.....	1
Local Context.....	1
Patient Care Rounds.....	3
Problem Statement.....	4
Supporting Framework.....	6
Project Purpose.....	7
REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....	9
Overview.....	9
Patient Care Rounds.....	11
Structure, Process, and Outcomes of Patient Care Rounds.....	12
Informational Tools: Standardized Checklists and the EHR.....	14
Interprofessional Collaboration.....	17
Teamwork and Collaboration.....	18
Communication.....	20
Patient-and-Family Centered Care.....	23
METHODS.....	26
Setting.....	26
Description of Project.....	26
Consideration of Evidence Related to Patient Care Rounds.....	27
Consideration of Evidence Related to Interprofessional Collaboration.....	28
Consideration of Evidence Related to Patient-and-Family Centered Care....	29
Implementation.....	29
Phase I.....	30
Phase II.....	31
Facilitating interdisciplinary collaboration.....	32

Electronic informational tool.....	32
Integration of patient and family centered care	33
Designing the pilot.....	35
Phase III	36
Structured observations of patient care rounds.....	36
Appreciative inquiry debriefings	37
Phase IV	37
Phase V	38
RESULTS	41
Results of Phase I and Phase II.....	41
Results of Phase III.....	42
Pilot Week 1.....	43
Pilot Week 2.....	44
Pilot Week 3.....	46
Pilot Week 4.....	47
Results of Phase IV.....	49
Final Element Consensus.....	49
Description of the New Process.....	51
Results of Phase V	54
Status at the End of the Pilot.....	54
Discussion.....	57
Structure and Process.....	58
Outcome Measures	62
CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	66
Recommendations for Practice	67
Recommendations for Ongoing Evaluation.....	68
REFERENCES	69
APPENDICES	81
A: E-MAIL FROM ORGANIZATION IRB.....	81
B: ORGANIZATIONAL IRB APPROVAL.....	82
C: ORGANIZATIONAL IRB STUDY INFORMATION SHEET	85
D: CSUF IRB APPROVAL.....	87
E: PROJECT SUMMARY DOCUMENT	88
F: 13-EVIDENCE INFORMED PRACTICES SUMMARY	94

G: ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES: MODIFIED SWOT	95
H: PROPOSED ELEMENTS FOR THE INFORMATIONAL TOOL.....	97
I: INFORMATIONAL TOOL: FINAL PILOT VERSION	98
J: INPUT AND FEEDBACK FROM BURN TEAM MEMBERS.....	99
K: STRUCTURED OBSERVATION TOOL	101
L: APPRECIATIVE INQUIRY 4-D MODEL.....	102
M: ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES: FINAL	103
N: PILOT DESIGN ELEMENTS.....	106
O: OBSERVATION AND APPRECIATIVE INQUIRY NOTES	108
P: STRUCTURED NOTE OUTPUT	116
Q: WEEKLY PATIENT CARE ROUNDS CHECKLIST	117
R: INFORMATIONAL TOOL CHANGES SUBMITTED.....	118
S: CURRICULUM FOR LOW-FIDELITY TEAM TRAINING.....	119
T: TABLES OF EVIDENCE	123

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Literature Search Specific Search Terms and Search Term Combinations.....	9
2. Total Number of Articles Used for Project.....	11
3. 13 Evidence-Informed Practices for Patient Care Rounds	27
4. Outcome Measure Monitoring Plan.....	39
5. Time Table for DNP Project Completion	40
6. Description of New Patient Care Rounding Process	53
7. Implementation of Evidence-Informed Patient Care Rounding	55
8. Outcome Measure Results	56
9. Challenges and Barriers to Interprofessional Collaboration.....	89
10. Challenges and Barriers to Patient-and-Family Centered Care.....	90
11. Review of Best PCR Practices.....	91
12. Planned Methods for Implementing Effective Elements of IPC	91
13. Outcome Measure Monitoring Plan.....	92
14. 13 Evidence-Informed Practices for Patient Care Rounds	94
15. Input and Feedback from Burn Team Members	99
16. Pilot Design Elements.....	106

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Supporting Framework: Inputs, Process, and Outcomes Model	8
2. Project Phases	30
3. Patient Story Elements in the Electronic Health Record	34
4. Schematic of Burn Unit	43
5. Elements of Effective Interprofessional Collaboration	89
6. Elements of Patient-and-Family Centered Care	90
7. Project Phases	92
8. Appreciative Inquiry Feedback Methodology	93
9. Appreciative Inquiry 4-D Model	102
10. Structured Electronic Note Output	116

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BACKGROUND

Patient care rounds represent a structure and process for collaboration and coordination among interdisciplinary team members who are caring for a group of patients in the acute care setting. The purpose of patient care rounding is for all members of the health care team to provide input into the medical and psychosocial plans of care for facilitating progression of care and providing an opportunity for shared decision making. Patient-centered care enhances collaboration and coordination by ensuring that patients and families are part of the decision-making process and patient values are included in plans of care (Institute of Medicine (U.S.) Committee on Quality of Health Care in America, 2001; Kitson, Marshall, Bassett, & Zeitz, 2013). Optimal outcomes in the acute care setting require implementation of best practices for patient care rounding into the structures and processes for patient-and-family centered interdisciplinary patient care rounds.

Local Context

The inpatient burn service at a 450-bed hospital can be considered part of a clinical microsystem. A clinical microsystem occurs when a group of people works together to care for a specific patient population; it is a complex adaptive system at the frontline of healthcare and is the point of care between the patient, the community, and the organizational macro-system (Nelson, 2011; Nelson, Batalden, & Godfrey, 2007; Nelson et al., 2002). Both adult and pediatric patients on the inpatient burn service may have burn injuries or other complex skin conditions, such as Steven Johnson's Syndrome, Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis Syndrome (TENS), and pemphigus vulgaris. These patients

require complex physiologic care, which includes elements of critical care and wound care, as well as compassionate psychological and emotional care.

According to the 2014 National Burn Repository Report (American Burn Association National Burn Repository, 2014), average charges for an inpatient stay were \$86,146 for burn survivors and \$285,225 for patients who die during hospitalization. Lengths of stay may be long with the average length of stay of 8 days between the years 2004 and 2013 for a burn patient. In fiscal year 2014 at our institution, total charges per case were \$205,951 with an average length of stay of 7.47 days. For fiscal year 2015, total charges per case were \$218,809 with an average length of stay of 8.65 days. Well-coordinated care at the microsystem level must occur because of the significant quality, safety, and cost outcomes associated with care of the burn patient.

Optimal outcomes in burn care are predicated on careful coordination among all burn team members working toward a common goal and ensuring that care is delivered in a collaborative, patient-centered approach where patients are considered part of the team (Al-Mousawi, Mecott-Rivera, Jeschke, & Herndon, 2009; Butler, 2013). Members for burn care include a core of physicians, nurses, and rehabilitation personnel (occupational therapy and physical therapy) along with key ancillary team members. Ancillary members may include licensed independent practitioners, pediatricians, psychiatrist, social workers, nutritional services, pharmacy personnel, respiratory care personnel, psychology personnel, child life personnel, or peer support personnel. The level and frequency of involvement of team members depends upon the individualized plan of care for each patient.

Patient Care Rounds

Patient care rounds is a method for collaboration among the health care team for the purpose of coordinating care and shared decision-making with the patient and/or family regarding the goals of care. Rounds are typically considered dedicated time when clinical information is reviewed and plans of care are developed for individual patients (Lane, Ferri, Lemaire, McLaughlin, & Stelfox, 2013). Currently, formal patient rounds for the inpatient burn service occurs daily with the physician team (attending physician, resident physician, physician assistant) and includes the bedside RN. The burn team also formally conducts weekly patient care rounds with the entire interdisciplinary core team and ancillary team members. Because this unit is a verified regional burn center accredited by the American College of Surgeons, weekly patient care conferences with all team disciplines present are required; these conferences (which may be patient rounds) must document patient progress and transitions of care (American College of Surgeons, 2014).

Team rounding or team collaboration is generally described as multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, or transdisciplinary. While these terms are often used interchangeably, multidisciplinary team refers to different professionals working on the same project but independently or in parallel; interdisciplinary team indicates collaboration between team members with integration of work; transdisciplinary indicates consensus-seeking professional practice amongst disciplines (D'Amour, Ferrada-Videla, San Martin, Rodriguez, & Beaulieu, 2005).

A well orchestrated team approach, based on elements of interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration, can enhance quality, safety, and cost outcomes associated

with the care of patients by reducing errors, promoting patient safety, and facilitating progression of care for patients. When accomplished, these outcomes would lead to decreased lengths of stay and long-term improvements in functional outcomes for patients.

Problem Statement

Patient care rounds are currently scheduled weekly each Monday among all burn team members for the purpose of coordinating care. Despite the availability of evidence-based guidelines and tools for effective, efficient, and patient-centered care rounds, implementation of these practices has not been evaluated. Although the scheduled weekly patient care rounds meets the standard for accreditation as a verified burn center and is the current process for burn team collaboration on the plan of care, this practice is based on a two-decade old practice of tradition rather than evidence. While it is understood that team approaches to patient care rounding are essential for care coordination and optimal outcomes, mere implementation of a patient care rounding process does not ensure that the communication and collaboration is efficient, effective, that the patient and family is included, or that optimal outcomes are automatically achieved.

Weekly patient care rounds are wrought with problems including those listed here:

- Ineffective communication among team members
- Lack of patient-centered approach
- Unclear roles and responsibilities of the team members during rounds
- Missed information regarding patient care
- Essential Team members not present during rounds

- Members leaving rounds early due to long length of the rounds
- Individuals present during rounds but without participation
- Unclear rationale for the presence of some individuals at rounds
- Missed documentation on the rounding documentation sheet that is part of the patient medical record
- Lack of clear direction and understanding of patient care goals at the completion of rounds.

Each Monday the physician team has scheduled visits with patients in the outpatient burn clinic. The outpatient rounds start at 10:00 am and end once the last scheduled patient has been seen. During this morning period the members of the inpatient burn team are supposed to fill out the current rounding tool with information each discipline wants to disseminate or discuss during the inpatient rounds. When rounding is completed in the outpatient setting a message via pager is sent out to the burn team to gather for rounds in the inpatient unit. The patient care rounds for the inpatients on the burn service can occur anytime after 10:00 am. The team gathers in front of the first patient room, the door to the patients' room is closed, and then discussions about the patients' care starts. The resident physician provides an overview of the patient history and then the attending physician proceeds to ask different members of the interdisciplinary team what issues, concerns, or comments they have regarding the patient care. Time spent on rounding for each individual patient is variable. When discussion is complete for a patient, the team either stays in the original location or moves to the next room; whether the team moves or not is based on the personal preference of the attending physician. Again, the door to the patient room is closed and the discussion among the

team members proceeds in the same manner as with the first patient. All patients located in the burn unit are discussed first and then patients who are located outside of the burn unit are discussed. Patient care rounds conclude when all patients on the burn service have been discussed. The informational tool with documentation from the pre-rounding period, and any notes written by the attending physician during rounds, is placed in the hard copy of the patients' medical record.

There is dissatisfaction by many members of the burn team who see rounds as merely being required as part of being a verified burn center and not leading to quality, safe, cost efficient care for patients. In fact, poor scores have been achieved for annual Agency for Healthcare Research & Quality (AHRQ) Survey on Patient Safety Culture for the burn unit nursing staff, particularly for the components of teamwork and communication. The continued reference by team members to the patient rounding process as weekly 'multidisciplinary rounds' may also demonstrate that the team has not made an intentional effort to evaluate the rounding process and evolve from a team that works in parallel to a team that integrates work by seeking professional consensus regarding the plan of care that includes the patient.

Supporting Framework

Patient care rounds occur within the context of the interdisciplinary team, with the intent to establish goals of care for the patient for the progression of care. The inputs, processes, and output/outcomes model was used to guide this performance improvement project. The inputs represent the core elements needed for implementation of the work processes for evidence-based, patient-and-family centered patient care rounds. The expected outcomes of the inputs and workflow processes are positive impacts on clinical

outcomes, patient and family satisfaction, healthcare provider satisfaction, and workflow efficiency outcomes through a standardized approach to collaborative care (see Figure 1).

Project Purpose

This performance improvement project assessed the structures and processes of weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds within the context of a burn service for adult and pediatric patients at the level of the clinical microsystem. Patient care rounding practices were evaluated for inclusion of best practices for patient-and-family centered care, and best practices for interprofessional collaboration. The goal of safe, quality patient-centered care was addressed by focusing on the following objectives:

- Identification and implementation of evidence-based practices for patient care rounding
- Enhanced interprofessional collaboration
- Incorporation of patient-and-family centered care into the patient care rounding process.

Figure 1. Supporting Framework: Inputs, Process, and Outcomes Model.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Overview

A review of the literature was conducted using PubMed, CINAHL, Cochrane library, Google Scholar, Agency for Health Care Research and Quality (AHRQ) website, and the Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) website. There were no date limitations for any of the search terms, with the exception of Google Scholar, which was limited to sources published between 2009 and 2015 because of the large number of articles retrieved and the desire to review the most recent articles that would be relevant to the current practice environments. All searches were limited to peer review articles in English. Articles were reviewed by title, abstract, and relevance of the subject for this project. The overarching topics used to design the literature search include patient care rounding, teamwork, collaboration, communication, patient-and-family centered care, and appreciative inquiry. Specific search terms, search term combinations for each topic, and total number of articles found include the following (see Table 1).

Table 1

Literature Search Specific Search Terms and Search Term Combinations

Topic	Search Term Combinations	Total Articles
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication AND nurse-physician relations • Team communication • Nurse-physician communication • Team-centered communication • Team communication AND ICU OR critical care OR intensive care • Nurse-physician communication AND nurse-physician relations AND ICU or critical care OR intensive care 	138
Relational Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relational Coordination 	129

Topic	Search Term Combinations	Total Articles
Patient Care Rounding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multidisciplinary rounds OR interdisciplinary rounds AND ICU OR critical care OR intensive care • Interprofessional patient care rounding • Patient-centered Rounding • Multidisciplinary rounds OR interdisciplinary rounds AND burn unit OR burn team • Patient care rounds AND facilitators • Multidisciplinary rounds OR interdisciplinary rounds AND communication AND teamwork AND collaboration 	288
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration AND teamwork AND interprofessional collaboration AND ICU or intensive care OR critical care • Collaboration AND Teamwork AND ICU OR Intensive Care OR Critical Care • Nurse-Physician Collaboration 	414
Patient-Centered Care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient centered care AND ICU OR critical care OR intensive care (peer reviewed, USA) • Patient centered care AND Multidisciplinary Rounds AND ICU OR critical care OR intensive care • Patient Centered Care AND Multidisciplinary Rounds AND ICU OR Intensive Care OR Critical Care 	83
Patient Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient outcomes AND teamwork AND ICU OR critical care OR intensive care 	162
Burn Teams	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multidisciplinary burn team AND burns • Burn teams AND burn centers 	178
Appreciative Inquiry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appreciative AND healthcare 	10
Google Scholar Search: 2009-2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication, collaboration and interdisciplinary patient rounding in the ICU 	1,850
Agency for Health Care Quality & Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive unit-based safety program 	NA
Institute for Healthcare Improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multidisciplinary rounds 	NA

Once the articles were reviewed for relevance to the project, the articles were organized into three main categories: (a) patient care rounds, (b) interprofessional collaboration, and (c) patient-and-family centered care. The literature was reviewed in the context of the three categories of evidence that will influence the development of a new structure, process, and outcome measures for interdisciplinary patient care rounding for the burn service (see Table 2).

Table 2

Total Number of Articles Used for Project

Category	Total Number of Articles Used
Patient Care Rounds	28
Interprofessional Collaboration	31
Patient and Family Centered Care	10

Patient Care Rounds

The literature supported the notion of patient care rounds as an essential element of safe, efficient patient care. How-to-guides with implementation and observational tools were obtained from the Institute of Healthcare Improvement and the Agency for Healthcare Improvement ([AHRQ], n.d.; Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2015). Terms used to describe patient care rounds include: (a) multidisciplinary rounds (b) interdisciplinary rounds, or more recently (c) interprofessional rounds. The term ‘patient care rounds’ is used to represent and describe the process of two or more disciplines coming together at regular intervals for the purpose of interdisciplinary planning of patient care. The literature regarding the composition of teams, the frequency of rounding, the structure of rounds, and the workflow process of patient care rounds is

highly variable. Elements regarding the structures, processes, and outcomes of patient care rounding as described in the literature, with secondary presentation of informational tools for patient care rounds as presented in the literature were evaluated for this project.

Structure, Process, and Outcomes of Patient Care Rounds

Two systematic reviews for patient care rounds identify core structures and processes that should be included, or should be considered for inclusion, into the patient care rounding process. Lane et al. (2013) identified a total of 13 evidence-informed practices for patient care rounds and Gurses and Xiao (2006) provided guidance on the development for structures, processes and outcome measures associated with patient care rounding. In both systematic reviews, authors noted difficulties with the ability to perform a meta-analysis because of the variability of methodologies among studies. Additionally, most studies were descriptive in nature and few randomized controlled trials exist.

The strongest evidence about interdisciplinary patient care rounding involved standardized structure and time, clear delineation of roles, a goal-oriented approach, and utilization of checklists to decrease the amount of information missed in patient care rounding discussions. Noise and interruptions have been identified as the most frequent barriers to patient care rounding, therefore reduction of nonessential activities and minimizing interruptions are key elements to consider in the implementation of patient care rounds. Gupta (2013) demonstrated that reducing interruptions during patient care rounds decreased patient care rounding time by 39%. The authors found that for a single episode of patient care rounding of 11.5 minutes, 22% of time spent was on activities other than rounding, and when interruptions were decreased, a single patient care

rounding event averaged 7 minutes per patient. Frequent interruption types include checking emails, interactions between team members aside from patient rounding, pagers, contacts from non-rounding team members, new patient arrival and/or departures, and interactions with consulting services. While not as strongly supported, the following elements show some positive impact on patient care rounds that should be considered for inclusion into patient care rounds:

- rounding in a conference room to increase efficiency and communication among the health care team
- rounding at the bedside to promote patient-and-family centered care
- encouraging an open and collaborative environment
- ensuring there is clear visibility between the health care team members during the rounding process
- promoting a team-based approach
- having a visual representation of the patient's information during the interdisciplinary rounds.

Outcomes of patient care rounds have been measured in a variety of ways with no clear evidence as to which outcome measures are best. In their systematic review, Gurses and Xiao (2006) found 32 different outcome measures for evaluating the effectiveness of information tools and processes for patient care rounding. The 32 measures were grouped into four categories: clinical outcomes; patient and family satisfaction; health care provider satisfaction; and work efficiency measures. These measures appear to represent a comprehensive list of types of outcomes that would be measured in the acute care setting for quality of care. The Interdisciplinary Rounds Assessment Scale (IDR

Assessment Scale) is the only tool found in the literature that directly measures the quality of interdisciplinary rounds (Ten Have et al., 2013). The tool was developed using Delphi Rounds and was determined to be reliable for elements of the patient plan of care and the process of patient care rounds.

Informational Tools: Standardized Checklists and the EHR

One element of standardization for patient care rounds includes informational tools. Gurses and Xiao (2006), based on systematic review, classified information tools as either patient-centric, process oriented, or decision support. These tools consisted of paper documentation, reference sources, and elements of an electronic medical record that were used for information gathering, documentation, or references for clinical information.

Demonstrating an overall positive impact, tools and checklists include rounding lists, rounding checklists, progress notes, daily goals checklists, daily goals sheets, discharge planning tools, and communication tools (Agarwal, Frankel, Tourner, McMillan, & Sharek, 2008; Centofanti et al., 2014; Gurses & Xiao, 2006; Hales & Pronovost, 2006; Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2015; Narasimhan, Eisen, Mahoney, Acerra, & Rosen, 2006; Phipps & Thomas, 2007; Pronovost et al., 2003; Seigel et al., 2014; Simpson, Peterson, & O'Brien-Ladner, 2007; Teixeira et al., 2013). Ainsworth, Pamplin, Rn, Linfoot, and Chung (2013) provide the one exception to the positive outcomes associated with structured informational tools, where implementation of a bedside communication tool did not change goal alignment among health care team members. While unusual for a research report to be published in the literature showing no significant results, the Ainsworth et al. (2013) article provides a glimpse into the idea that

careful consideration must be made when implementing new information tools. Unit culture, structures, and work processes (clinical microsystem) must be carefully considered in the implementation of any informational tools. Standardized checklists and tools have been identified as essential elements for patient care rounds, but there is no single tool, checklist, or methodology (paper documentation or electronic medical record) that is identified in the literature for ideal structure, process and outcomes. Based on quantitative, qualitative, and human factors analysis methodology of network visualization, Collins et al. (2014) identified 11 discrete data elements used for informational tools for patient care rounding. The 11 clinical data elements included:

- plans
- patient-identifying information
- consultations
- results
- problems
- medications
- procedures
- short-term concerns
- past medical/surgical history
- goals
- admission demographics.

This was the only study that evaluated the elements to include in an informational tool rather than evaluating the impact of a specific tool for various outcomes measures in a health care setting.

Current efforts to fully implement an electronic health record (EHR) is largely driven by recommendations of the Institute of Medicine (U.S.) Committee on Quality of Healthcare in America (2001). This committee recommends elimination of handwritten clinical data and implementation of all three stages of Meaningful Use, which is a Medicare and Medicaid Electronic Health Record Incentive Program that provides financial incentives for the meaningful use of certified EHR technology to improve patient care (Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services, 2014). A major barrier of the use of the EHR in patient care rounds is that the technology in the current design status is built for the single-user and does not support collaboration, shared decision making, shared goal development, and multiuser interfaces (Gurses & Xiao, 2006; Morrison, Jones, Blackwell, & Vuylsteke, 2008). The design of patient care rounds should consider the impact of documentation of the patient care rounds in the EHR and how best to facilitate teamwork and collaboration in the context of the potential barriers. Design of patient care rounds should consider how communication and collaboration are impacted as informational tools are integrated into the electronic environment.

Overall, informational tools, whether on paper or in the electronic environment, improved communication processes and outcomes and are supported as part of the patient care rounding. However, there is no consensus as to the content of informational tools. Each recommended practice should be evaluated for inclusion into the clinical microsystem for three aspects: (a) which elements of patient care rounding should be introduced, including specific informational tools (b) how to implement the elements and informational tools within the context of the interdisciplinary team and (c) how to

measure the impact of the of patient care rounding for clinical and efficiency outcomes, as well as satisfaction outcomes for patients, families, and healthcare providers.

Interprofessional Collaboration

Interprofessional collaboration is the culmination of teamwork, collaboration, and communication, which are essential for achieving efficiency and quality within a team (Institute of Medicine [U.S.] Committee on Quality of Healthcare in America, 2001; Wheelan, Burchill, & Tilin, 2003). Despite recognition that effective interprofessional collaboration is essential for improved care outcomes, success at integrating elements of effective communication and collaboration into organizational work structures and processes is difficult and teams can be at varying stages of development. Difficulties in communication, coordination, and relationships among interprofessional health care members were documented as early as 1967 in *The Doctor Nurse Game* (Stein, 1967); these issues remain important as noted by a call for better interprofessional collaboration in order to obtain enhanced quality of care (Committee on the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation Initiative on the Future of Nursing at the Institute of Medicine, 2011). Gender differences, differences in discipline-specific training, unequal status among team members, unequal benefits for team participation, varying levels of personal commitment to group process, and role confusion have also been associated with poor interprofessional collaboration (Crawford, Omery, & Seago, 2012; Lancaster, Kolakowsky-Hayner, Kovacich, & Greer-Williams, 2015; Schoefield & Amodeo, 1999; Stein, 1967; Woodward & House, 1997). Perceptions of nurses having an insignificant power based in relation with physicians (Coombs, 2003), perceptions that nurses are not colleagues or key collaborators by resident physicians (Weinberg, Miner, & Rivlin,

2009), and discrepancies of perceptions where physicians rate the quality of collaboration with nurses 40% higher than nurses rate quality of collaboration with physicians (Azoulay et al., 2009) are all examples of poor interprofessional collaboration. Poor interprofessional collaboration results in job strain, animosity, mistrust, and poor communication. Barriers to interprofessional collaboration can be classified according to three themes: relationships, systems, and communication (Costello & Thompson, 2015).

Teamwork and Collaboration

Teamwork and collaboration reflect a dynamic process of leadership, sharing, partnership, interdependence, and power and are often viewed within the framework of inputs, processes, and outputs (Bosch et al., 2009; D'Amour et al., 2005; Dietz et al., 2014; Paradis et al., 2013; Reader, Flin, Mearns, & Cuthbertson, 2009; West & Lyubovnikova, 2013). Leadership characteristics that impact safety and teamwork include style and adaptability of leaders in critical situations (Manser, 2008). Sharing and partnership implies that members of all disciplines are equal in their involvement and ability to contribute to care planning and decision-making. Interdependence represents the idea that outcomes could not be achieved without individual team members working together, but recognizes that each discipline makes a unique contribution based upon professional scope. Power refers to shared-power, where teamwork is based upon nonhierarchical relationships. Inputs include characteristics of the individual, team, leader, task, and environment (context). Processes include transitional processes such as planning and problem solving, task processes, individual processes such as competency and attitude, and interpersonal relations and communications, where problems and conflicts are addressed.

Interventions that have shown to improve effective teamwork and collaboration include interprofessional meetings, interprofessional rounding, standardized rounding processes with daily goals, and team training to enhance teamwork skills (Dietz et al., 2014; Ponte, Gross, Milliman-Richard, & Lacey, 2010; Sharma & Klocke, 2014; Zwarenstein, Goldman, & Reeves, 2009). More specifically, Costa, Barg, Asch, and Kahn (2014) identified clinical protocols, checklists, and supportive information technology as structural facilitators of interprofessional collaboration in the intensive care unit. There is also opportunity for team difficulties to become learning and team development opportunities when open discussions occur allowing difficulties and conflicts to be aired in a more informal manner (Kvarnstrom, 2008).

There is no clear evidence as to the best way to measure organizational and clinical outcomes relative to teamwork and collaboration. Individual measures identified include:

- numbers of adverse events
- mortality
- length of stay
- quality of end of life care
- unit efficiency
- compliance with protocols
- staff satisfaction
- job satisfaction
- staff morale
- stress

- burn out
- staff turnover
- technical competency
- cost of care.

The individual measures can be categorized into two or three major categories: (1) patient (clinical) outcomes and team outcomes or (2) patient (clinical) outcomes, team outcomes, and organizational outcomes.

Interprofessional collaboration can be operationally defined as “an interpersonal process characterized by healthcare professionals from multiple disciplines with shared objectives, decision-making, responsibility, and power working together to solve patient care problems; the process is best attained through an interprofessional education that promotes an atmosphere of mutual trust and respect, effective and open communication, and awareness and acceptance of the roles, skills, and responsibilities of the participating disciplines” (Petri, 2010, p. 79).

Communication

Communication is one of the most prominent constructs in the literature for teamwork and collaboration (Dietz et al., 2014) and has been widely studied in healthcare literature, particularly in respect to relationships between nurses and physicians. A sender encodes a message, the message is transmitted via a message channel, and receiver decodes the message. Message channels can be either synchronous or asynchronous; synchronous may include face-to-face or telephone communication and asynchronous can include written communication or voice messages.

Types of channels used for communication, noise and interruptions, and the context of communication (how the message is encoded or decoded) are factors in miscommunication and communication failures (Dayton & Henriksen, 2007). Medical errors have been attributed to miscommunication and communication errors and may be related to hierarchy and power issues in healthcare team relationships, lack of trust and respect between health care providers, gender differences, lack of information, decoding errors due to the mode of communication, and lack of team-centered communication strategies (Matzke, Houston, Fischer, & Bradshaw, 2014; Sutcliffe, Lewton, & Rosenthal, 2004; Tjia et al., 2009). Power can be exerted in communication via silence, telling others what to do, speaking frequently, or by being argumentative (Gardezi et al., 2009; Matzke et al., 2014; Van Ess Coeling & Cuker, 2000). The EHR, an asynchronous mode of communication, has been noted as a contributor to ineffective communication due to missed communication (Robinson, Gorman, Slimmer, & Yudkowsky, 2010; Sutcliffe et al., 2004).

The commonly identified facilitators to effective communication include openness, understanding, equal participation, clarity, collaborative problem solving, respect, understanding of roles, active listening, and a team-centered “we” approach to solving problems (Apker, Propp, Zabava, Ford, & Hofmeister, 2006; Cypress, 2001; Manojlovich & Antonakos, 2008; Matzke et al., 2014; Robinson et al., 2010; Van Ess Coeling & Cukr, 2000). Interestingly, even though health care providers prefer synchronous communication as opposed to asynchronous communication (Costello & Thompson, 2015), a study analyzing time spent in synchronous communication demonstrated that nurses spent only 24% of a 12-hour shift in synchronous (face-to-face)

communication (Tschannen et al., 2013). Therefore, time spent in different modes of communication must be considered when implementing interventions to improve healthcare provider communication.

Healthcare providers and teams must find common ground by developing clear channels of communication grounded in shared goals, shared knowledge, and mutual respect. Keys to success are establishing nonhierarchical, structured communication that encourages open participation and a team-centered approach that focuses on shared responsibility for tasks and problem solving. Effective communication can be operationally defined as "...the ability to transmit accurate, comprehensible, consistent, reliable, culturally competent, balanced, repeated information through a common system according to a common set of rules in an open timely manner toward positive health care outcomes" (Cypress, 2011, p. 36).

There is no 'one-size-fits-all' approach to how a particular team should work together in order to ensure effective communication and collaboration in the context of the clinical microsystem. Each team within the clinical microsystem team must evaluate the facilitators and barriers to determine how those elements can be implemented, or minimized, to assure the best outcomes for patient, families, and healthcare providers. Outcomes for communication are typically measured by satisfaction with communication, the effects of communication on collaboration, or patient care outcomes related to effective communication via teamwork and collaboration (Manojlovich & Antonakos, 2008; Manojlovich, Antonkos, & Ronis, 2009; Van Ess Coeling & Cukr, 2000).

Patient-and-Family Centered Care

Patients and families must be part of the decision-making process in healthcare decisions. However, this is not always easy to achieve and not consistently practiced. Patient-centeredness is one recommendation of the 2001 Institute of Medicine Report, “Crossing the Quality Chasm” (Institute of Medicine (U.S.) Committee on Quality of Health Care in America, 2001). A search of the literature on patient-centered care revealed four systematic and literature reviews (Cypress, 2012); Kitson et al., 2013; Mastro, Flynn, & Preuster, 2014; Sidani & Fox, 2014) and one clinical practice guideline developed by the Society of Critical Care Medicine (Davidson et al., 2007). The reviews and the clinical practice guidelines span from a focus on pediatrics only, to a focus on adults only, to a focus on both pediatric and adult patients. The term patient-and-family centered care will be used to express the concept of patient-centeredness.

Caring, trusting, and nurturing relationships are the foundations of patient-and-family centered care as the patient and family enter the acute care environment (Mastro et al., 2014; Sidani & Fox, 2014). This is done with active listening and actively seeking input from the patient and family, which naturally flows into the incorporation of the patient and family into participation during patient care rounds. Facilitating participation of patients and families in patient care rounds with a clear schedule for rounding and team roles clearly identified, promotes shared decision-making and collaboration with the entire health care team (Carayon et al., 2014; Davidson et al., 2007). Full partnership between patient, family, and health care providers is achieved when there is open communication about individual physiologic and emotional components of care based on identification of patient-centered goals where the patient and family are able to ask

questions and clarify information (Kitson et al., 2013; Mastro et al., 2014; Sidani & Fox, 2014). The outcomes of patient-and-family centered care have shown overall positive effects for patients, families, and health care providers. Majority of concerns regarding patient-and-family presence revolve around privacy and confidentiality, the perception that health care provider communication may be limited or constrained, and concerns that the amount of teaching for resident physicians will decrease (Cypress, 2012).

The concepts and ideas of patient-and-family centered care are relatively simple in nature, but much more complex to integrate into the delivery of care. Barriers to implementing patient-and-family centered care include lack of a common understanding of teamwork and placing the patient at the center of care, lack of time and workload pressures to make patient-and-family care a reality, a focus on task-based aspects of care rather than a holistic approach to patient care, and contextual factors where rules and norms are perceived by families as done to maintain order or for staff convenience, rather than safety (Baird, Davies, Hinds, Baggott, & Rehm, 2015; Esmaeili, 2014). Evidence of the disconnect between the practice and principles of patient-and-family centered care are demonstrated in the use of medical jargon, unilateral rather than bilateral introductions from the healthcare team, information sharing that does not translate to shared decision-making, and the healthcare provider-centric timing of patient care rounds (Carayon et al., 2014; Subramony, Hametz, & Balmer, 2014).

Measuring the outcomes of patient-and-family centered care has been done in a variety of ways and addresses both process and outcomes of patient-and-family centered care. Mastro et al. (2014) identified patient satisfaction, health care provider satisfaction, quality, safety, self-care, and healthcare costs as categories of outcome measures for

patient-and-family centered care. Examples of these measures include perceived stress, readiness to learn, length of time for patient-and-family centered rounds, understanding of patient care plans, perceptions of teamwork, and hospital acquired infections.

The integration of the components of patient-and-family centered care result from the health care teams' thoughtful deliberation about how to integrate the principles, which starts with engaging patients as full partners of the team.

METHODS

Setting

Census for the inpatient burn service varies, but ranges from 6 to 20 patients. The patient population includes both adult and pediatric patients who are either classified as intensive care or acute care status. The in-patient setting is an 8-bed unit and when the census is higher than 8 patients, burn service patients are placed in beds in various units throughout the hospital. Members of the interdisciplinary team include the following: assistant burn coordinator, burn program manager, burn trauma administrative analyst, case manager, child life specialist, clinical nurse specialist, dietician, infection control practitioner, nurse educator, nurse manager, assistant nurse manager, bedside nurse, wound care nurse, charge nurse, occupational therapy, palliative care physician, pediatric intensivist, pharmacist, physical therapy, physician, physician assistant, psychologist, resident physician, respiratory therapist, social worker, and a speech therapist. Throughout the week these team members work independently and interdependently to perform discipline specific tasks to facilitate patient progress. Weekly patient care rounds with the interdisciplinary team are done for team discussions and coordination of patient care.

Description of Project

Patient care rounds for the burn service in our organization did not follow evidence-based guidelines, practices, or best practices for patient care rounding. The patient care rounds also did not include patient-and-family centered care or enhance interprofessional collaboration in an intentional way. Patient-and-family centered evidence-based practices during patient care rounding for weekly interdisciplinary patient

care rounds on in inpatient burn service were implemented. A team consensus approach was used to discuss the structural, process, and outcome components of rounding in order to promote interprofessional collaboration and shared decision-making. A 5-phase implementation and monitoring plan was followed.

Consideration of Evidence Related to Patient Care Rounds

Evidence-based practices based on the 13 evidence-informed practices (Lane et al., 2013) for patient care rounds were used to determine pre-rounding expectations, how the team gathers for rounds, how the patient information would be presented, how the discussion would flow, how the goals of care were decided, and how the rounds would be documented (see Table 3).

Table 3

13 Evidence-Informed Practices for Patient Care Rounds

	Element	Recommendation
1	Implement multidisciplinary rounds (including at least a medical doctor, registered nurse, and pharmacist	
2	Standardized location, time, and team composition	
3	Define explicit roles for each health care provider participating on rounds	
4	Develop and implement structured tool (best practice checklist)	Strong – definitely do it
5	Reduce nonessential time wasting activities	
6	Minimize unnecessary interruptions	
7	Focus discussions on development of daily goals and document all discussed goals in health record	
8	Conduct discussions at bedside to promote patient-centeredness	
9	Conduct discussions in conference room to promote efficiency and communication	
10	Establish open collaborative discussion environment	
11	Ensure clear visibility between all healthcare providers	Weak – probably do it
12	Empower healthcare providers to promote team-based approach to discussions	
13	Produce visual presentation of patient information	No specific recommendation

An additional element considered for inclusion into this project was the implementation of an electronic informational tool into the patient record. The electronic informational tool was redesigned from the previous paper documentation tool to have a focus on patient-centered goals, rather than discipline-centric documentation tool and considered the 11 discrete data elements presented in the Collins et al. (2014) article.

Consideration of Evidence Related to Interprofessional Collaboration

Interventions that have demonstrated improvements in teamwork include: interprofessional meetings, interprofessional rounding, standardized rounding processes with daily goals, and team training to enhance teamwork skills. The main intervention of this project was the standardization of rounding processes, but also included interprofessional meetings for team decision-making.

Since April 2015, a new monthly performance improvement meeting was integrated into the structure of the burn team. This meeting includes representatives from each discipline on the burn team and meets monthly. This monthly meeting was used as the main venue for the team approach for shared decision making about the concepts of evidence-based patient care rounds, interprofessional collaboration, and patient-and-family centered care.

As noted earlier, keys to success in communication between health care providers include establishing nonhierarchical, structured communication that encourages open participation and team-centered approach. Tasks must be approached as shared responsibility. While developing the approach to effective teamwork and collaboration, the focus was put into the design of the electronic informational tool as the first step to moving from a team working in parallel (multidisciplinary) to an integrated team

(interdisciplinary or transdisciplinary). A more effective approach to team-centered patient care was promoted by designing the electronic informational tool to be patient-centric rather than discipline-centric. Focus was placed on team action rather than individual specific action so that the strategies of team communication were included (Matzke et al., 2014).

Consideration of Evidence Related to Patient-and-Family Centered Care

During project planning and implementation the focus included how to make patient care rounds more patient and family centric and how to integrate the patient and family centric elements into rounding. A large percentage of the discussions regarding patient-and-family centered care were focused on how to bring the patient and family into the rounding process without decreasing the efficiency of the rounding process.

Ultimately the team decided to get input from the patient and family and to input that information into the electronic informational tool. The input from the patient and family was projected to influence the patient care goals developed and influence the actions to be taken after the weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds.

Implementation

This implementation of evidence-based practices for patient care rounding was done in five phases. These are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Project Phases.

Phase I

Phase I included submitting the Institutional Review Board (IRB) application to both the organizations IRB and California State University Fullerton (CSUF) IBR, reviewing the current rounding practices, and reviewing the literature with the burn team. The IRB at the organization where this project was completed defines research as “a systematic investigation, including research development, testing and evaluation, designed to develop or contribute to generalizable knowledge” (The Regents of the University of California, 2014). A systematic investigation is identified as a prospective plan with data collection and data analysis to answer a question. A project is considered generalizable when the project results in a formal presentation or publication. Based upon the organization’s description an IRB and the intent to submit an abstract for a national burn association professional organization conference, IRB approval was required for this project (see Appendix A). The organizations IRB was submitted in full on July 13, 2015. The organizations IRB requested several revisions and additions. One significant addition

was the inclusion of a study information sheet to be distributed to the staff during weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds (see Appendix C). The final IRB approval as exempt status was obtained on September 23, 2015 (see Appendix B). The CSUF IRB application was written and submitted for approval on October 8, 2015. Final approval from the CSUF IRB was obtained on October 16, 2015 (see Appendix D).

Review of the current state of patient care rounding for the burn service and review of relevant literature was started in July 2015. The review of the current state was discussed with the interdisciplinary team during the monthly burn performance improvement meeting and during regularly schedule inpatient unit monthly staff meetings. The initial presentation to the team at the burn performance improvement meeting on July 14, 2015 included the following content:

- current patient care rounding practices
- project purpose, review of the literature
- project approach and methods
- process and outcome measures
- introduction to elements of Phase II.

Copies of the project summary document (see Appendix E) from the meetings and the tables of evidence (see Appendices T-V) were made available to the participants as printed hard copies and also sent through e-mail for the team to review.

Phase II

The focus of phase II was on redesign of structure, process and outcomes of weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds and occurred simultaneously while awaiting the final approval of the IRB application by both the organizations' IRB and CSUF IRB.

Input was obtained during both the monthly interdisciplinary burn performance improvement team meeting and during the weekly Monday interdisciplinary patient care rounds to ensure that input from a majority of burn team members was obtained. Burn performance improvement meetings were held prior to the pilot on July 28, August 25, and September 22, 2015 and the performance improvement project was discussed each meeting to ensure that the topic was maintained as an important focus for the burn team.

Facilitating interdisciplinary collaboration. Discussions and decisions were facilitated with the development of three documents: (a) a list of the 13 evidence-informed practice related to patient care rounding (see Appendix F) (b) a modified SWOT analysis for defining roles and responsibilities (Appendix G) and (c) a list of proposed elements for a patient-centered interdisciplinary informational tool (see Appendix H). The three documents were created as a visual for the topics that were discussed with the group during the meetings. The three documents were also distributed via e-mail to facilitate as much input from team members and allowed input and feedback via a variety of methods. The documents were made available during the monthly burn performance improvement meetings and during the weekly interdisciplinary rounds each Monday throughout phase II and prior to the implementation of the pilot.

Electronic informational tool. Meetings were initiated in early July 2015 to brainstorm an electronic patient-centered interdisciplinary information tool for documentation of the interdisciplinary plan of care with the clinical informatics team at the organization. Available evidence regarding patient-centric elements and standard content for information tools were included in the development of the draft electronic documentation tool for interdisciplinary patient care rounds (Collins et al., 2014; Gurses

& Xiao, 2006) and used to develop the draft version of the document (see Appendix H). Meetings were held on July 7, July 17, and August 5, 2015 with the clinical informatics team to determine the best format and design for the electronic informational tool. A draft version was created in the electronic environment and a demonstration of the electronic informational tool was provided to the team on August 25, 2015 during the monthly burn performance improvement team meeting. Feedback was obtained from the group and modifications made by the clinical informatics specialists. A final pilot version (see Appendix I) was completed with a final testing of functionality on October 1, 2015. The document was named “Interdisciplinary Plan of Care Rounds” and is available in the electronic health record for use as a structured note.

Integration of patient and family centered care. One of the most important and challenging aspects was determining how to incorporate patient-and-family centered goals of care into the weekly interdisciplinary rounds. Discussions and feedback were obtained regarding whether to include and invite patients and families to participate in the patient care rounding process. Concern was voiced regarding the time constraints of patient care rounds and the increase in time that may be added to the interdisciplinary patient care rounding process. Concern was also voiced about not having a venue to discuss difficulties and challenges related to care of the patient and family during rounds, impacting the ability to have open and honest communication among the burn team members (see Appendix J); ultimately the team agreed that the patient and family input and goals of care were important to the process. The team decided that including the patient story in the interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note would promote a patient-and-family centered focused component to the team discussion while maintaining

efficiency of time. The team came to consensus that the patient and family input would be obtained prior to interdisciplinary rounding time, entered into the electronic note, and then discussed during the interdisciplinary patient care rounds. The following categories related to patient-and-family centered care were included in the final pilot version of the interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note (see Figure 3):

- patient concern while in the hospital
- most important thing that will make a difference in patient safety
- personal treatment goal
- what do you know about your treatment plan
- how would parents/others like to participate in care
- what questions/concerns do you/child have about you/your child's health or care.

Patient Story

What are your concerns while in the hospital?
What is the most important thing that will make a difference in your hospital stay?
What is your personal treatment goal?
What do you know about your treatment plan?
How would you like to participate in your care?
What questions/concerns do you have about your healthcare?
What are your priorities? Your family's priorities?
Other information?

Figure 3. Patient Story Elements in the Electronic Health Record.

In-services for the new electronic informational tool were held October 14, October 16, and October 19, 2015 for all nursing staff. Specific in-services were held for nursing staff since the goal was to have nursing staff members initiate the patient story during the Sunday night shift. The in-service outlined expectations and workflow and how the process would be operationalized for entering and obtaining the patient story.

Designing the pilot. The information gathered during the monthly burn performance improvement meeting and weekly during regularly schedule interdisciplinary patient care rounds was used to define the structure and process of the pilot. Based on review of all the discussion, input, verbal feedback, and written feedback, a recommendation for the 4-week trial was developed and approved by the burn team (see Appendix J). A 4-week trial period was chosen in order to have each of the two full-time burn service attending physicians participate in the trial for a total of two weeks each. The other members of the burn team were to be present during all four weeks of the trial. The trial was designed as follows:

- 2-weeks of with attending physician A
 - Week 1: rounding according to current method of rotating as a group to stand outside of the doorway of each patient room or gathered at the nurses station,
 - Week 2: rounding conference room setting in the burn unit workroom.
- 2-weeks with attending physician B

- Week 3: rounding according to current method of rotating as a group to stand outside of the doorway of each patient room or gathered at the nurses station,
- Week 4: rounding conference room setting in the burn unit workroom.

The rationale for having each attending physician attend both a session of interdisciplinary patient care rounding using the traditional method and during the trial of a conference room setting was to be able to have the group compare and contrast the differences between both methods with each of the full-time burn service attending physicians.

Phase III

Phase III included implementation of the pilot and spanned 4-weeks and was implemented on October 19, 2015 and concluded on November 9, 2015. Weekly evaluation of the patient care rounding process was completed using the structured observational tool (see Appendix K) and appreciative inquiry debriefings (see Appendix L).

Structured observations of patient care rounds. Observations of the interdisciplinary patient care rounding were done to evaluate teamwork and communication (see Appendix K). The members of the burn team chosen as observers were those whose presence on rounds was determined to be non-integral to the process of providing input into the plan of care. The clinical nurse specialist for critical care and the burn program manager were chosen as optimal team members to provide the observations. The structured observation tool was adapted from the AHRQ “Observing Patient Care Rounds” observation tool (AHRQ, n.d.; Lyons et al., 2013), the Jefferson

Interprofessional Clinical Rounding Project (Lyons et al., 2013), and the evidence-informed patient care rounding practices (Lane et al., 2013).

Appreciative inquiry debriefings. Appreciative inquiry was used after each weekly rounding episode to facilitate changes in patient care rounds for the burn team and to elicit feedback from burn team members (see Appendix L). Appreciative inquiry was chosen to facilitate affirmation, appreciation, and dialogue among the team regarding the patient care rounding structures and processes. The debriefing sessions were designed to be relatively short and last approximately 2-5 minutes. The questions posed at the conclusion of rounds were:

1. Discover:
 - a. What were the strengths of patient care rounds today?
 - b. What do you value most about the patient care rounding experience?
2. Dream
 - a. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on patients and families?
 - b. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on the healthcare team?
3. Design: Is there anything that could make patient care rounds even better?
4. Destiny: How do we work to sustain patient care rounding practices?

The feedback was written down weekly and recorded (see Appendix O).

Phase IV

Phase IV occurred at the conclusion of the pilot on November 9, 2015. This phase included finalizing the components of the weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds

and submitting changes to the clinical informatics team for the electronic interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note. The structured note was modified according to feedback and input from the entire burn team during the pilot phase. Phase IV also focused on sustaining the changes that were agreed upon by the team during the pilot phase and ensuring that all team members, particularly those that were not present during the rounds (i.e. night shift nursing staff), were aware of the pilot, the results of the pilot, and expected practice. Communication regarding the results of the pilot and expected practice occurred at unit staff meetings, weekly during interdisciplinary rounds, and monthly at the burn performance improvement meeting.

Phase V

The focus for phase V is on the sustainability of the new structure and process and includes continuous monitoring of the outcome measures. The main outcome for this project was to ensure that the seven essential elements of evidence-based patient care rounds were implemented into practice and selected elements of the remaining six evidence-based practices were implemented into practice in order to enhance interprofessional collaboration and incorporate patient-and-family centered care. Other outcome measures chosen for this project were based on the four categories of clinical outcomes, patient and family outcomes, health care provider satisfaction, and work efficiency outcomes (Gurses & Xiao, 2006) (see Table 4).

This project will remain a standing agenda item on the monthly burn performance improvement monthly team meeting for both continued reinforcement of the goals of the patient care rounds and to continue to gather input and feedback from the team. Updates

will include aspects of sustainability and progress on outcome measures. A timeline for phase completion is outlined in Table 5.

Table 4

Outcome Measure Monitoring Plan

	Outcomes Measures	Monitoring Plan
Clinical	Decreased length of stay (LOS)	Monitoring for LOS for fiscal year 2014, 2015, & 2016
	Increase in near miss error reporting	Baseline will be 1 year prior to implementation of pilot date
	Decrease in errors	Baseline will be 1 year prior to implementation of pilot date
Patient and family satisfaction	Maintain or increase patient satisfaction scores in the domains of the overall rating and willingness to recommend	Press Ganey® scores will be monitored monthly, quarterly, and yearly
Care provider satisfaction	Improved scores on the teamwork and communication categories for the AHRQ Hospital Culture of Safety Survey	AHRQ survey in October 2015
Work efficiency	Decrease in interruptions and distractions during interdisciplinary rounding	Noted decrease in interruptions on the observational tool during the pilot
	Maintenance of an acceptable average rounding time per patient	Total rounding time divided by the total number of patients include in the burn team weekly rounding each Monday

Table 5

Time Table for DNP Project Completion

Component		Dates
	DNP project proposal defense	May 15, 2015
Phase I	IRB Approval	Approved by organization: September 23, 2015 Approved by CSUF: October 16, 2015
	Review of current state & Review of literature	July 14, 2015
Phase II	Informational tool design, integration of interprofessional collaboration, integration of patient-and-family centered care, & pilot design	July 28, August 25, and September 22, 2015
Phase III	Pilot	October 19 to November 9, 2015
Phase IV	Make revisions as needed	November 16, 2015 final rounding process implemented November 16, 2015 submission of changes to electronic interdisciplinary plan of care December 16, 2015 go-live date of the electronic interdisciplinary plan of care revisions
Phase V	Monitoring of process and outcome measures	In process and ongoing

RESULTS

The first four phases of the five-phase project have been completed and the fifth phase is currently in progress. The first four implementation phases addressed the specifics of patient care rounding, roles and responsibilities, enhancing interprofessional collaboration, enhancing patient-and-family centered care, and measuring the impact of the of interdisciplinary patient care rounding. The last phase is ongoing and will specifically address sustainability and continuous monitoring of outcome measures.

Results of Phase I and Phase II

The first two phases were integral components for the team to work and make decisions together that considered the evidence. During phase I and II the following was accomplished: team discussions of the current literature, team discussion on what and how the elements of evidence-based practice would be incorporated into practice, the design of the electronic informational tool, and how patient-and-family centered care would be integrated into the weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds.

The longer than expected IRB approval period from the organization allowed for four months of discussion about the project and the desired approach for the pilot. Multiple discussions over time allowed for team members to discuss their concerns about the pilot and ideas to incorporate into the pilot more in depth than might have otherwise been done during a shorter timeframe. Delays in the IRB approval also led to both the pilot and the implementation of the electronic version of the interdisciplinary plan of care structured note to occur at the same time, which originally was not thought to be an option for this project due to the backlog in clinical informatics and projected timeline for full implementation of the electronic structured note. The pilot design was truly

collaborative and occurred over a sufficient amount of time that allowed individual team members to give input in a variety of methods. Ultimately the team was committed to trying the new method and comfortable with the approach by the time the pilot started.

Results of Phase III

The substantial lead-time between the initiation of discussions about the project and the start of the Phase III allowed for the pilot to be carried out as designed. During the first pilot week attending physician A rounded according to the traditional method of rotating as a group and gathering around the nurses' station. Week 2 was conducted with attending physician B according to the traditional method of rotating as a group and standing outside each patient room with the door closed. Pilot Week 3 rounding occurred with attending physician B and was conducted in the burn unit workroom as a conference room setting. Pilot Week 4 was conducted with attending physician A and was conducted in the burn unit workroom in a conference room setting (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Schematic of Burn Unit.

Pilot Week 1

During the first week of the pilot there was a delay in the implementation of the electronic interdisciplinary plan of care structured note, therefore the paper documentation tool was used during the first week. In the usual manner, the members of the interdisciplinary team documented their notes and interventions on the paper document. The team interdisciplinary rounding commenced at 2:30 pm, they agreed upon standardized rounding time. The rounding took place first starting on side A of the unit and focused on the four patients on side A. After side A was complete the group moved to side B using the back hallway and discussed the four patients and side B (rounds progressed from room 1 to room 8). The doors to the patient rooms were closed during

the rounding process. The patients who were located outside of the burn unit were discussed while the group gathered on side B around the nurses' station.

During interdisciplinary rounds the two observers, the clinical nurse specialist and the burn program manager, each took notes using the observational tool. Once patient rounding was complete the appreciative inquiry questions were used as prompts to guide the discussion about the interdisciplinary patient care rounds that week. Notes were taken and recorded for both the observations and the appreciative inquiry process (see Appendix O). As a result of week 1, no substantial changes were made to implement in Pilot Week 2, but the process of announcing the pilot and announcing that observations did lead to more burn team members expressing how frequently distractions occurred and the significant number of interruptions that took place during rounds. A few members provided feedback that they really could not hear all of the conversation that occurred during the rounding process and missed some of the information discussed during interdisciplinary rounds.

Pilot Week 2

The electronic interdisciplinary plan of care was ready for use. The nurse working the Sunday night shift prior to the interdisciplinary patient care rounds initiated the electronic interdisciplinary plan of care and input the elements of the patient story based on discussion with the patient and family on to the structure note. On Monday morning the day shift nurse confirmed the information in the patient story section and updated the information as necessary. On Monday morning members of the interdisciplinary team accessed the burn interdisciplinary patient care structured note and entered goals and interventions according to their assessments. The team rounding commenced at 2:30 pm.

During Pilot Week 2, the team started at room 1 on side A and then moved to each subsequent room (progressing from room 1 to room 8) until the last patient on side B was discussed. Doors were closed for each patient room as the rounding was conducted. The patients who were located outside of the burn unit were discussed while the group congregated on side B near the nursing station after the discussions for patient located in the unit were completed. A member of the burn team recorded notes on the electronic interdisciplinary plan of care structured note. One member of the burn team was assigned to record the rounding information based on the single-user interface that restricted one person at a time to open the electronic structured note. The output of the structured note was Available in the electronic medical record (see Appendix P).

Like Pilot Week 1, the burn program manager and the clinical nurse specialist were designated observers and each took notes using the observational tool. Once patient rounding was complete the appreciative inquiry questions were used for prompts to guide the discussion about the interdisciplinary rounds that week. Notes were taken and recorded for both the observations and the appreciative inquiry process (see Appendix O).

As a result of Pilot Week 2 no substantial changes were made to implement in Pilot Week 3, but the conversation and feedback continued to indicate how many distractions and interruptions took place during rounds. The group verbalized that the majority were looking forward to the interdisciplinary patient care rounding process on week 3 as the group transitioned to having interdisciplinary patient care rounds in a conference room setting.

Pilot Week 3

During the Sunday night shift the night shift nurses spoke with the patients and initiated the interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note. The nurses working the Sunday night shift prior to the interdisciplinary patient care rounds initiated the electronic structured note and input the elements of the patient story based on discussion with the patient and family. On Monday morning the day shift nurse confirmed the information in the patient story section and updated the information as necessary. During the Monday morning hours various members of the burn team opened the electronic structured note and filled out the goals and interventions as appropriate. The interdisciplinary patient care rounds were scheduled to start at 2:30 pm. The unit secretary was put in charge of displaying the photos on a workstation on wheels and opening up the appropriate photos for each patient care rounding episode. The display of the photos was used for visualization of the burns or wounds that were being treated in the hospital. As each patient was discussed the interdisciplinary plan of care structured note was used. The charge nurse was assigned to record the plan of care for each patient care rounding episode. The attending physician B, using a paper guideline of the interdisciplinary plan of care structured note, led the discussion. The most challenging aspect was changing the approach of the discussion from discipline-centric based on the paper documentation tool to topic-centric based on the prompts on the structured note. The attending physician defaulted to the pre-pilot format out of habit despite having the topic prompts from the electronic note. The rounds had a more patient-centered focus during pilot week 3, but the overall rounds took longer. Notes were taken and recorded for both the observations and appreciative inquiry process (see Appendix O).

Feedback based on the appreciative inquiry debriefings indicated that the rounds were quieter and this was positive, but participants indicated that the group discussion could still be more focused if the prompts were followed. The group commented that the documentation of the interdisciplinary patient care rounds would be improved if the electronic note were visible to team members during rounds. The team suggested that the order of the topics on the electronic structured note may need to be re-sequenced, but wanted to try the rounding process again prior to making a final decision. As a result of Pilot Week 3, determination was made to display both the patient photos and the interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note for all burn team members to see during the rounding process. The team thought that it would facilitate the groups' understanding of the flow of the electronic structured note and promote a more standardized approach to the documentation.

Pilot Week 4

During the Sunday night shift the nurses spoke with the patients and initiated the interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note. The patient story was initiated and the information entered on the structured note. On Monday morning the day shift nurse confirmed the information in the patient story section and updated the information as needed. During the Monday morning hours various members of the burn team opened the note and filled out the goals and interventions as appropriate. The patient care rounds were scheduled to start at 2:30 pm and the team gathered in the burn unit workroom at 2:30 pm. The electronic interdisciplinary plan of care structured note was projected using a LCD projector so that all burn team members were able to visualize the note as the discussion was held and documentation occurred. The team decided to project the note as

the discussion took place as a way to overcome the problems of single-user interface, which restricts one user at a time to open the note. Photos of each patient were displayed using a workstation on wheels for visualization of the patients' burns and wounds. The discussion was team oriented and discussion was guided by the prompts of the electronic structured tool. The interdisciplinary patient care rounds continued to have a patient-centered focus and lasted for one hour. Notes were taken and recorded for both the observations and appreciative inquiry process (see Appendix O).

Feedback based on the appreciative inquiry debriefing indicated that the rounds were much more efficient being conducted in the workroom. Additional feedback indicated that there was a decrease in distractions and the conversation was more focused. General consensus from the group indicated that our process of redesigning the rounding structure and process had made a positive impact on the interdisciplinary patient care rounds. Projecting the electronic interdisciplinary plan of care structured note helped overcome the single-user interface issues and allowed all members to see what was being documented during the patient care rounding process.

During the 4-week pilot period feedback was incorporated and trialed during the subsequent weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounding. Feedback was used to modify the rounding process each week so that changes and improvements in the rounding process were incorporated in real time. This iterative process of incorporating weekly feedback in real time helped to improve the patient care rounding process as the pilot progressed. This real time incorporation of feedback demonstrated to the team that their feedback and suggestions were used to improve the rounding process.

Results of Phase IV

Final Element Consensus

At the conclusion of the pilot the final rounding structure and process were agreed upon and put into place:

- Defined roles and responsibilities for burn team members established (see Appendix M).
- Clear guidelines for which roles were considered essential for participating were developed (see Appendix M).
- The burn workroom was identified as the standardized location (see Appendix J).
- A start time of 2:30 pm was identified as the standardized time for interdisciplinary patient care rounds (see Appendix J).
- A structured patient-centered, goal-centered interdisciplinary plan of care electronic note was designed and implemented (see Appendix I).
- Display of both the patients' burn and wound photos and the interdisciplinary plan of care structured note were implemented during the rounding time for each patient.
- The night shift nursing staff initiated the interdisciplinary plan of care structured note with the patient story component to promote patient-centeredness.
- A page initiated each Monday morning by the unit secretary or charge nurse to ensure participation of the following disciplines as necessary, based on

patient population each week (see Appendix Q): child life specialist, pediatric pharmacist, and the pediatric intensivist.

- Burn Interdisciplinary patient care rounds checklist was designed and implemented (see Appendix Q)

Other changes for the structure and process of interdisciplinary patient care rounding were suggested, but were not able to be implemented in real time. Those changes consisted of (a) modifications to the electronic interdisciplinary plan of care round structured note and (b) ensuring communication with the patient and family after rounds about the plan of care for the week. The following elements were submitted to clinical informatics on November 16, 2015 (see Appendix R) and were made available in the electronic environment on December 16, 2015:

- Adding an Activities of Daily Living (ADLs) section on the interdisciplinary plan of care structured note.
- Changes to the anticipated discharge date so that the date could be copied from the previous weeks structured note.
- Moving the plan for surgery section to the discharge planning area of the structured note since the plan for surgery significantly impacts the projected discharge date.

The final process for sharing the top goals and priorities with the patient and family after the rounding process included implementing a post-rounding conversation with the patient and family regarding the plan of care. The bedside nurse was appointed to share the results and goals for the week with the patient and family.

The culmination of both the observations and appreciative inquiry debriefing were discussed during the November 24, 2015 burn performance improvement meeting. Initial results for outcome measures were presented and the submitted changes to the electronic interdisciplinary structured note were presented. Feedback was elicited and the group agreed that new structure and process enhanced weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds for the burn service. The team agreed to the final structure and processes that was developed during the pilot period.

Description of the New Process

The pilot resulted in a revised structure and process for the weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds for the burn service. The components of the weekly interdisciplinary rounding include: pre-rounding structure and process, how the team gathers for rounds, how the information is presented, the flow of discussions, how goals of care are decided, and how rounds are documented (see Table 6). Burn interdisciplinary rounding process is initiated the night prior to rounding and the night shift nurse starts the conversation with the patient and family to obtain the patient story. The night shift nurse initiates the electronic interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note and inputs the information regarding the patient story. On Monday morning the burn unit charge nurse reviews the burn interdisciplinary patient care rounds checklist that was created (see Appendix Q). On Monday morning members of the burn team access the interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note and can pre-input expected goals and interventions on the note. The unit charge nurse or the unit secretary sends a page to each of the indicated burn team members as noted on the burn interdisciplinary patient care rounds checklist around 8:30 am. The burn unit secretary or charge nurse sets up the burn

unit workroom at 2:00 pm by setting up the projector and workstation on wheels to project the electronic burn interdisciplinary plan of care structured note and the patient photos.

The team gathers in the burn unit workroom at 2:30 pm. The pediatric patients are discussed first and the adult patients are discussed after the discussion of all pediatric patients is concluded. Discussion of pediatric patients first in the rounding process allows the child life specialist, pediatric intensivist, and the pediatric pharmacist to join rounds for the pediatric patients without having to stay during the rounding episodes for the adult patients. During each rounding episode one team member pulls up the patients' burn and wound photos so that the team can visualize the wounds. The structured note is projected on a screen so that all team members are able to visualize the prompts and inputs from the rounding discussion. The rounding episode begins with the physician team providing a brief description of the patient condition and includes the reason for admission and current physiologic status. Routinely it is the resident physician who provides the initial patient overview. Once the physician team concludes the brief overview, the patient story documented on the electronic note is reviewed. After the patient story is reviewed the remainder of the plan of care prompts are followed and discussed; any burn team member can provide information pertinent to any rounding element for any of the discussion prompts. At the completion of the patient care rounding episode the team moves on to discuss the next patient and this process continues until all patients have been discussed. The interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note is available in the patient electronic medical record for review by all team members after rounds is completed and can be reviewed by any member of the burn team throughout the week.

Table 6

Description of New Patient Care Rounding Process

Component	Description of new process
Pre-Rounding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The electronic interdisciplinary plan of care structured note is initiated the night before the Monday afternoon interdisciplinary patient care rounds • The night shift nurse completes the patient story portion of the structured note • On Monday morning the charge nurse and unit secretary review the burn weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounding checklist (see Appendix Q) • During Monday morning hours members of the burn team members review patient information and input any key issues or information on the electronic interdisciplinary plan of care structured note • The unit secretary prepares the conference room with the projector and the workstation on wheels at 2:00 pm
Gathering the Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The charge nurse page the indicated team members as noted on the Burn Weekly Interdisciplinary Patient Care Rounding Checklist before 10:00 am • Standardized start time for burn interdisciplinary patient care rounds is 2:30 pm in the burn unit work room
Presenting information during rounds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pediatric patients are discussed first (regardless of location), then adult patients in the burn unit, lastly adult patients located outside of the burn unit • When there are no pediatric patients in the burn unit adult patients are discussed first and then the patients located outside of the burn unit • As each patient is presented the interdisciplinary patient care rounds structured note and the most recent photos of the patients burns and wounds are displayed
Flow of discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A member of the physician team (attending physician, physicians' assistant, resident physician) presents a brief patient history • The bedside nurse presents the patient story • The prompts are followed for discussion point the rounding episode • If a particular prompt is not pertinent to a patient, the prompt is skipped
Deciding Goals of Care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At the conclusion of the discussion of each patient's top care priorities are documented in the last section of the electronic note • The bedside RN discusses the top care priorities with the patient and family
Documentation of Rounds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each week a team member is assigned to record the discussion on the interdisciplinary plan of care for each patient • Team members present during the interdisciplinary patient care rounds are indicated on the burn interdisciplinary patient care rounds structured note with a check mark

Results of Phase V

Phase V is currently in progress and is focused on the sustainability of the new structure and process and includes continuous monitoring of the outcome measures. This project will remain a standing agenda item on the monthly burn performance improvement monthly team meeting for both continued reinforcement of the goals of the interdisciplinary patient care rounds and to continue to gather input and feedback from the team.

Status at End of Pilot

The status of the implementation of each of the elements related to evidence-based patient care rounding is seen in Table 7. The results of the outcome measure monitoring plan are shown in Table 8.

Table 7

Implementation of Evidence-Informed Patient Care Rounding

Element	Measure	Result	
1	Implement multidisciplinary rounds (including at least a medical doctor, registered nurse, and pharmacist)	Essential members are identified (see Appendix G)	Implemented
2	Standardized location, time, and team composition	Rounds starts on time and essential members are present (see Appendix G, Appendix K, Appendix P)	Implemented
3	Define explicit roles for each health care provider participating on rounds	Roles and responsibilities are defined (see Appendix G)	Implemented
4	Develop and implement structured tool (best practice checklist)	Patient-centered interdisciplinary information tool is implemented (see Appendix I)	Implemented
6	Minimize unnecessary interruptions	Monitored via observational tool for evaluation of patient care rounds (see Appendix K)	Achieved and continues to be monitored
7	Focus discussions on development of daily goals and document all discussed goals in health record	Goals are documented on patient care rounds informational tool (see Appendix I)	Implemented
8	Conduct discussions at bedside to promote patient-centeredness	Inclusion of this element to be discussed by burn performance improvement team (see Appendix J)	Not implemented
9	Conduct discussions in conference room to promote efficiency and communication	Inclusion of this element to be discussed by burn performance improvement team (see Appendix J)	Implemented
10	Establish open collaborative discussion environment	Monitored via observational tool for evaluation of patient care rounds (see Appendix E)	Achieved and continues to be monitored
11	Ensure clear visibility between all healthcare providers	Inclusion of this element to be discussed by burn performance improvement team	Not Implemented
12	Empower healthcare providers to promote team-based approach to discussions	Monitored via observational tool for evaluation of patient care rounds (see Appendix I)	Achieved and continues to be monitored

Table 8

Outcome Measure Results

Outcomes Measures		Results
Clinical	Decreased length of stay (LOS)	LOS FY 2014 = 7.47 days LOS FY 2015 = 8.65 days LOS FY 2016 = in progress
	Increase in near miss error reporting	Unable to obtain accurate baseline – did not measure this outcome
	Decrease in errors	Unable to obtain accurate baseline – did not measure this outcome
Patient and family satisfaction	Maintain or increase patient satisfaction scores (Overall rating and Recommend the hospital – Press Ganey®). Results are based on burn unit specific data.	Press Ganey® Scores FY 2014 = <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall rating – 100% • Recommend the hospital – 80% Press Ganey® Scores FY 2015 = <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall rating – 66.7% • Recommend the hospital – 66.7% Press Ganey® Scores FY 2016 (July – December, 2015) = <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall rating – 100% • Recommend the hospital – 100%
Care provider satisfaction	Improved scores on the teamwork and communication categories for the AHRQ Culture of Safety Survey (Higher percentage is better)	Pre-project Teamwork within unit = 76% Communication openness = 39% Post-project Teamwork within unit = TBD Communication openness = TBD
Work efficiency	Decrease in interruptions and distractions during interdisciplinary rounding Maintenance of an acceptable average rounding time per patient (Total rounding time divided by the total number of patients rounded on per week) No standard acceptable rounding time exists in the literature.	Noted decrease in interruptions on the observational tool during the pilot (see Appendix O) During the pilot October 19, 2015 = 5.5 minutes per patient. Total of 10 patients. Rounds 2:30 pm to 3:30 pm. October 26, 2015 = 6.25 minutes per patient. Total of 8 patients. Rounds 2:30 pm to 3:30 pm. November 2, 2015 = 5.41 minutes per patient. Total of 12 patients. Rounds 2:40 pm to 3:45 pm. November 9, 2015 = 7 minutes per patient. Total of 5 patients. Rounds 2:33 pm to 3:10 pm.

Post-pilot

November 16, 2015 = 7.5 minutes per patient.
Total of 8 patients. Rounds 2:33 pm to 3:30 pm.

November 23, 2015 = 9.3 minutes per patient.
Total of 8 patients. Rounds 2:40 pm to 3:55 pm.

November 30, 2015 = 9 minutes per patient. Total
of 10 patients. Rounds 2:40 pm to 4:05 pm.

December 7, 2015 = 8.75 minutes per patient.
Total of 8 patients. Rounds 2:30 pm to 3:40 pm.

Discussion

The goals of this project were aimed at enhancing safe, quality, and patient-centered care. The interventions implemented to achieve the goals included evidence-based practices for patient care rounding, enhancing interprofessional collaboration using shared decision-making, and incorporating patient-and-family centered care into the patient care rounding structures and processes for our interdisciplinary teams' weekly interdisciplinary rounding. Process and outcome measures were used to evaluate the project interventions. Sparse availability of relevant literature and very limited validated tools for measuring patient care rounds made the selection of process and outcome measures challenging. Selection of process and outcomes measures was based on the evidence provided by Lane et al. (2013), Gurses and Xiao (2006), and outcome measures based on organizational priorities and key metrics for the burn program. The results demonstrated integration of a majority of the 13 evidence-informed practices for patient care rounding, the integration of an electronic interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note, the use of shared decision-making for the interdisciplinary team, and implementation of patient-and-family centered approach to patient care rounding. The evaluation of clinical, patient satisfaction, care provider satisfaction, and work efficiency

outcomes did not result in immediately available data to demonstrate that the measures were impacted by the interventions of this performance improvement project. The exception was work efficiency outcome, which was measured and evaluated at the conclusion of every weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds.

Structure and Process

The structure and process of the interdisciplinary patient care rounding demonstrated improvement with the implementation of eleven of the 13 evidence-informed practices for patient care rounding, including all of the elements that had the strongest evidence as described by Lane et al. (2013). A key factor of success was the adaptability of leadership as described by Manser (2008) that allowed shared decision-making to determine the new structure and process of patient care rounds rather than changes dictated by the leadership team, or rounding practices based on the personal preference of the attending physicians. The process of using shared decision-making to systematically determine which of the 13 evidence-informed elements to include in the team patient care rounding process demonstrated a move from a team working independently, a more multidisciplinary approach, to a team working in parallel, a more interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approach as describe by D'Amour et al. (2005). At the end of the pilot a clear structure was developed with protocols, checklists, and supportive informational technology, identified as structural facilitators by Costa et al. (2014); these protocols, checklists, and supportive information technologies are available to all team member to review and can easily be shared with new team members. Every member of the team is able to identify the structure of pre-rounding tasks with an available checklist (see Appendix Q), which team members should be present during

rounds (see Appendix M), and the expected flow to the rounding discussions (see Appendix R).

This project did not result in a full partnership between the patient, family, and health care providers as described by Kitson et al. (2013), Mastro et al. (2014), and Sidani and Fox (2014); however, significant progress was made by the team. Full partnership between the patient, family, and healthcare providers would have resulted in the patient and family being part of the rounding process; since the team was in the process of developing from a multidisciplinary team mindset to an interdisciplinary team mindset, the additional work to full partnership with the patient and family in the time frame allotted for the pilot was not achievable. The newly developed electronic interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note allowed for documentation of patient-centered goals in the patient record and documenting the “voice of the patient” with the patient story element. Nightshift nursing staff now participates in the weekly interdisciplinary rounding process as they gather the patient story and document the story in the structured note on a weekly basis. During the pilot a few team members suggested further enhancements to the inclusion of the patient and family and wanted to share the top priorities and goals with the patient and family after the conclusion of rounds. This suggestion resulted in changes to the structured note to include a section called “top priorities and goals” (see Appendix R) that is available to the bedside nurse to review with the patient and family after the interdisciplinary team concludes patient care rounds. A better process for identification of patient-centered goals was developed, but the concept of the patient and family being able to ask questions and clarify information during interdisciplinary patient care rounds was not included in the interdisciplinary

patient care rounding process. A future goal will be for the team will be to determine how to include the patient and family in the rounding process. A potential process measure that should be considered is follow-up with the patient and family to evaluate their understanding of the patient plan of care for the week. Obtaining real time feedback from patients and families seems an appropriate and important measure to demonstrate the positive impact planning of patient care has for patients and families.

While 11 of the 13 evidence-informed practice elements were implemented, there were two elements that the team chose not to implement. These two elements include (a) conducting discussions at bedside to promote patient-centeredness and (b) ensuring clear visibility between all healthcare providers. Both of these elements were considered to have a weak level of evidence to support the practice and were indicated as “probably do it” by Lane et al. (2013). The team chose the interdisciplinary rounding in a conference room setting with visualization of patient information and patient photos, rather than patient care rounding at the bedside. As an alternative to having rounds at the bedside, the goal is to discuss the top priorities and goals with patients and families after the team rounding process to promote patient-centeredness. The size of the conference room prevents clear visibility, but this was considered acceptable because the team agreed that viewing the electronic interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note and the patient photos. Secondly, the process of projecting the electronic interdisciplinary plan of care structured note and the patient photos helped to overcome the barrier of the single-user interface of the EHR, a factor that has been noted to decrease collaboration (Gurses & Xiao, 2006; Morrison et al., 2008).

The observations made during the rounding process and appreciative inquiry debriefings provided an approach for team members to provide feedback focused on the positive, what was working, rather than on the negative, or what was not working. The pilot allowed for reflection regarding the traditional method and provided an opportunity for team members to speak about issues that may have previously gone unsaid. For example, the high number of interruptions and distractions was something that many team members commented upon either during group discussions or during informal conversations among team members. The traditional approach was so engrained that even if team members disliked the number of distractions and interruptions, an alternative to the traditional interdisciplinary rounding process was never considered.

The outcomes of the structure and processes that were implemented and identified as improved are clearly identifiable to the team and are easily demonstrated to the team with a table that shows which elements were implemented (see Table 7). The structure and process outcomes of the 13 evidence-informed practices are also supported by the results of the study by Ten Have et al. (2013), which indicated discussion at rounds should include the main problem, the diagnostic plan with formulation of goal(s), review of long term interventions and the patient's greatest risk. Additionally, this is the time to clarify consultant expectations and encourage the input of junior physicians and nursing staff. The rounds should include a clear summary with clear roles for task performance. These elements are essential indicators for assessing the quality of interdisciplinary rounds. The process measures appear to be the most critical measures for demonstrating to the team that real changes, based on team input, suggestions, and feedback made a difference to how our teams' interdisciplinary rounds are conducted.

Outcome Measures

Outcome measures are an important part of any performance improvement project to determine if the predefined goals have been met. Additionally, the outcomes measures can be an indication of quality and safety, demonstrating that the improvements contribute to effective care for patients. Outcome measures for this project were selected from the 32 measures discussed by Gurses and Xiao (2006) and based on key organizational goals and priorities. The outcome measures were grouped into the categories of clinical outcomes, patient and family satisfaction, health care provider satisfaction, and work efficiency measures.

The clinical outcomes of decreasing length of stay, increasing near miss medication errors, and decreasing medication errors were difficult to achieve during the project timeline. Decreasing length of stay is an important outcome, but will need to be monitored over time to determine if an overall decrease is achieved. Many factors influence the length of stay and while planning of patient care is a critical element, desired results may be realized over a longer period of time than was realistic based on the project's timeline.

Early in the course of this project it became clear to the team leadership that not all near miss and errors were being reported. Based upon the realization that our reporting was not as accurate as desired, the clinical outcome measures for errors were determined not to be an ideal measure for this project. Any work during the patient care rounding implementation process on addressing near miss and errors would have complicated the implementation process. Consideration of increasing near miss errors and reducing errors as a part of the interdisciplinary patient care rounding process is still considered an

important objective for the team because of the relationship of errors to hierarchical relationships, miscommunication, and communication errors (Sutcliffe et al., 2004; Tjia et al., 2009). Efforts to increase near miss reporting and decrease errors will be considered once the implementation of the patient care rounding process is stabilized and sustained for a period of time.

Patient and family satisfaction outcomes were measured using the results of the Press Ganey® Scores. Scores were monitored from fiscal year 2014, 2015, and 2016. The selection of the Press Ganey® overall rating and recommend the hospital rating were chosen based on the organizations goals that were focused on these two components. Initial results show improved ratings during fiscal year 2016, but the results only show the months of July to December 2015. As noted above, a potential measure that should be considered is follow-up with the patient and family to evaluate their understanding of the patient plan of care for the week in order to obtain real time feedback from patients and families.

Care provider satisfaction was to be measured by the communication and teamwork sections of the AHRQ Culture of Safety Survey. The survey was to be administered October 2015, however the survey was delayed by the organization and rescheduled for March 2016. This is an important measure to better evaluate the interprofessional collaboration with an objective and validated measure. Although this measure is delayed, it is still considered an important measure and will be evaluated when results are available in April or May 2016. There is also opportunity for team difficulties to become learning and team development opportunities when open discussions occur, allowing difficulties and conflicts to be aired in a more informal

manner and this can be done with interprofessional education (Kvarnstrom, 2008). A curriculum for low-fidelity team training simulation was developed for use at a later date (see Appendix S) for the purpose of team training on aspects of teamwork and communication. The curriculum was developed based on the elements of TeamSTEPPS® (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ), n.d.).

Gupta (2013) demonstrated that reducing interruptions during patient care rounds decreased patient care rounding time by 39%. Work efficiency outcomes for this project were measured by calculating the total rounding time by the total number of patients. The average rounding time per patient during the pilot was 6.04 minutes with an average of 8.6 minutes the four weeks following the pilot. While the Gupta (2013) study demonstrated a 22% reduction in rounding time from 11.5 minutes to 7 minutes, this project did not show the same reduction in rounding time. Despite the lack of decreased time in rounding time during this project, the overall impression of the burn team is that the quality of rounds has improved and that interruptions have decreased. It appears that the rounding time has remained relatively consistent but with noted improvements and a more patient-centered focus. One area of needed improvement for the team is staying on topic with what the outlined elements and discussion prompts on the interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note. Patient care discussions went out of order with the structured note when team members interjected information that did not stay on topic. While the off topic discussion was often pertinent to caring for the patient, it seems that this can prolong the patient care rounding as the team can get side-tracked on information that is non-essential for the development of the weekly plan of care for the patient. The changes to the interdisciplinary plan of care rounds structured note are expected to reduce

the deviation from the discussion prompts. Nevertheless, even with the extraneous or off-topic discussion the team indicated that the length of rounds and discussions for each patient seem an appropriate length, as indicated by the feedback by team members.

Overall, the clinical, patient and family satisfaction, care provider satisfaction, and work efficiency outcomes were more difficult to evaluate for their effectiveness based on the project timeline. However, these measures are critical for patient safety and quality and will need to be monitored long term. As noted earlier, there is no clear evidence of which outcome measures are best, so our team chose outcome measures that represented either organizational goals, organizational priorities, or measures the burn team determined were indicators good quality of care for burn patients. Continued prioritization of these measures will need to be done to evaluate appropriateness in relation to team and organizational priorities.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Optimal outcomes for burn patients' occur when care is well coordinated and includes the patient and family. As a verified burn center, weekly patient care conferences are required, must be documented, and must indicate patient progression and transitions of care. This project aimed to incorporate current evidence related to patient care rounding into our teams' weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds. Using a team-centered approach to decision-making and reviewing the relevant evidence and practices, our team was able to re-define our weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds and move toward a more interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approach to care. Changes in practice for a two-decade old tradition seem to have been achievable because of the consideration of the facilitators and barriers related to teamwork and communication within the team culture and the context of the clinical microsystem. Team decision-making allowed for team members to give input and feedback in a structured way that had never been done before. Real time changes based on feedback allowed team members to see that their input was taken seriously and integrated into practice. Real change has been achieved, however it is apparent that further progress and improvements are possible.

One of the most important lessons of this process was the discussions and learning in the informal environment of the patient care rounding process. The team was able to progress and improve in the context of the regular work environment with open discussion of what worked well and what needed to change. As the weeks of the pilot progressed more and more team members were able to voice their preferences for aspects important in the team rounding process. Essentially, the process of evaluating the

traditional practices associated with interdisciplinary patient care rounds for the burn service led to more open discussions and a better approach to shared decision-making.

Patient-and-family centered care was a major challenge. Like the literature suggests, barriers to implementing patient-and-family centered care are numerous. This project demonstrated an overall discomfort with including the patient-and-family in patient care rounds, even though the desire was to get the patient and family input. While progress was made and interventions to move toward shared decision-making, a healthcare-centric approach to patient care rounding for the burn service still exists to some extent. Thoughtful reflection indicates that incremental steps to a full partnership of health care providers with the patient-and-family during patient care rounding is probably the most realistic and achievable approach.

The results demonstrate achievement of the desired goals for this project, but also illustrate that implementing evidence-based practices requires continuous improvement and strong leadership to engage all members of the group.

Recommendations for Practice

Recommendations to further enhance patient care rounding include:

1. Including the patient and family during rounds.
2. Team training using an interprofessional communication skills lab to enhance respect, decrease role confusion between various professionals, and invite additional, active participation from all team members.
3. Periodic scheduled observations of interdisciplinary patient care rounds using the structured observational tool for monitoring of sustainability of implemented practices.

4. Developing a plan for more accurate reporting of near miss errors and actual errors with the team.

Recommendations for Ongoing Evaluation

Many of the outcome measures identified for this project must be measured over a longer period of time than this project allowed. Monitoring for sustained improvements is essential. Recommendations for ongoing evaluation for the implemented changes include:

1. Further evaluation of the quality and safety interdisciplinary rounds should include
 - a. direct measurement of patient care rounds (i.e., IDR Assessment Scale)
 - b. increased near miss error reporting
 - c. decreased error reporting
 - d. patient and family feedback on the plan of care and teamwork.
2. Continued data collection for outcome measures, such as
 - a. length of stay
 - b. patient satisfaction
 - c. care provider satisfaction, work efficiency.

Sustainability and creating an environment that continually strives to improve the structures, processes, and outcomes of patient care rounding will be the focus moving forward for the team.

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APPENDIX A**E-MAIL FROM ORGANIZATION IRB**

From: Roy Taggug [mailto:rtaggug@uci.edu] Sent: Friday, April 24, 2015 5:17 PM To: Baldwin, Brooke Cc: Joe, Victor Subject: Confirmation of Activities that Constitute Human Subjects Research

BROOKE BALDWIN-RODRIGUEZ
BURN UNIT, UC IRVINE MEDICAL CENTER

RE: Activities that Constitute Human Subjects Research

The University of California, Irvine (UCI) Human Research Protections Program complies with all review requirements defined in 45 CFR Part 46, Protection of Human Subjects. 45 CFR 46.102(e) defines research as “a systematic investigation, including research development, testing and evaluation, designed to develop or contribute to generalizable knowledge; and 45 CFR 46.102(f) defines a human subject as “a living individual about whom an investigator conducting research obtains 1) data through intervention or interaction with the individual; or 2) identifiable private information.” Private information must be individually identifiable (i.e., the identity of the subject is or may readily be ascertained by the investigator or associated with the information) to meet the definition of human subject.

The UCI Human Research Protections (HRP) staff reviewed the information you submitted pertaining to your project and concluded that the currently untitled project, as described, does qualify as human subjects research. Therefore, UCI IRB review and approval is required prior to initiating the research. Although the IRB will make the final determination, based on the information you provided the research would likely qualify for Exempt review. For additional information about the IRB submission process, please go to the How to Submit Electronic IRB (e-IRB) Application for Review web page.

If you have any questions or concerns, please feel free to contact me.

Sincerely,

Roy Taggug
IRB C Analyst

cc: Faculty Sponsor – Dr. Victor C. Joe

Roy Taggug
Institutional Review Board “C” Analyst

UCI Office of Research
5171 California Avenue, Suite 150

Irvine, CA 92697-7600
rtaggug@uci.edu
949-824-6662

APPENDIX B
ORGANIZATION IRB APPROVAL

UC IRVINE: OFFICE OF RESEARCH INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD (IRB)
PAGE 1 OF 2

CONFIRMATION OF EXEMPT RESEARCH REGISTRATION
September 23, 2015

BROOKE BALDWIN-RODRIGUEZ DEPARTMENT OF TRAUMA/CRITICAL
CARE/BURN SURGERY

RE: HS# 2015-2193 Implementing Evidence-Based Practice for Interdisciplinary
Rounding: Performance Improvement Project

The human subjects research project referenced above has been registered with the UC Irvine Institutional Review Board (UCI IRB) as Exempt from Federal regulations in accordance with 45 CFR 46.101. This exemption is limited to the described activities in the registered UCI IRB Protocol Narrative and extends to the performance of such activities at the sites identified in your UCI IRB Protocol Application. Informed consent from subjects must be obtained unless otherwise indicated below. UCI IRB conditions for the conduct of this research are included on the attached sheet.

Information provided to prospective subjects to obtain their informed consent should, at a minimum, consists of the following information: the subject is being asked to participate in research, what his/her participation will involve, all foreseeable risks and benefits, the extent to which privacy and confidentiality will be protected, that participation in research is voluntary and the subject may refuse to participate or withdraw at any time without prejudice.

Questions concerning registration of this study may be directed to the UC Irvine Office of Research, 5171 California Avenue, Suite 150, Irvine CA 92697-7600; 949-824-6068 or 949-824-2125 (biomedical committee) or 949-824-6662 (social-behavioral committee).

Level of Review: Exempt Review, Category 2

Determinations as Conditions of Exemption:

Informed Consent Requirements:

1. Informed Consent Not required – burn patient group
2. Signed Informed Consent Not Required – clinician/provider group
 - a. Study Information Sheet Required

Alyssa A. Brewer, MD, PhD Vice-Chair, Institutional Review Board

Registration valid from 09/18/2015 to 09/17/2018 UCI (FWA) 00004071, Approved:
January 31, 2003

UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA
UC IRVINE: OFFICE OF RESEARCH INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD (IRB)
PAGE 2 OF 2

UCI IRB CONDITIONS FOR ALL UCI HUMAN RESEARCH PROTOCOLS

UCI RESEARCH POLICIES: All individuals engaged in human-subjects research are responsible for compliance with all applicable UCI Research Policies (<http://www.research.uci.edu/compliance/human-research-protections/hrp-policy-library/hrppPolicies.htm>). The Lead Researcher of the study is ultimately responsible for assuring all study team members adhere to applicable policies for the conduct of human-subjects research.

LEAD RESEARCHER RECORDKEEPING RESPONSIBILITIES: Lead Researchers are responsible for the retention of protocol-related records. The following web pages should be reviewed for more information about the Lead Researcher's recordkeeping responsibilities for the preparation and maintenance of research files: <http://www.research.uci.edu/compliance/human-research-protections/researchers/lead-researcher-recordkeeping-responsibilities.html> and <http://www.research.uci.edu/compliance/human-research-protections/researchers/preparation-maintenance-research-audit-file.html>.

PROTOCOL EXPIRATION: The UCI IRB expiration date is provided on the exempt registration letter. All exempt protocols are registered for a maximum period of 3 years. If the study will continue beyond 3 years, a new Application for IRB review is required. No annual continuing renewals are required.

MODIFICATIONS & AMENDMENTS: No changes are to be made to the registered protocol or the approved, stamped consent form without the prior review and approval of the UCI IRB. All changes (e.g., a change in procedure, number of subjects, personnel, study locations, new recruitment materials, study instruments, etc.) must be prospectively reviewed and confirmed by the IRB before they are implemented.

APPROVED VERSIONS OF CONSENT DOCUMENTS, INCLUDING STUDY INFORMATION SHEETS: Unless a waiver of informed consent is granted by the IRB, the consent documents (consent form; study information sheet) with the UCI IRB approval stamp must be used for consenting all human subjects entered into this study. Only the current approved version of the consent documents may be used to consent subjects. Approved consent documents are not to be used beyond their expiration date.

ADVERSE EVENT & UNANTICIPATED PROBLEMS REPORTING: All unanticipated problem involving risk to subjects or others or serious adverse events must be reported to the UCI IRB in accordance with Federal regulations and UCI policy. See <http://www.research.uci.edu/compliance/human-research->

protections/researchers/reporting-of-adverse-events-unanticipated-problems-and-violations.html for complete details.

CHANGES IN FINANCIAL INTEREST: Any changes in the financial relationship between the study sponsor and any of the investigators on the study and/or any new potential conflicts of interest must be reported immediately to the UCI Conflict of Interest Oversight Committee (COIOC). If these changes affect the conduct of the study or result in a change in the required wording of the approved informed consent document, then these changes must also be reported to the UCI IRB via a modification request.

CLOSING REPORT: An electronic closing report should be filed with the UCI IRB when the research concludes. See <http://www.research.uci.edu/compliance/human-research-protections/researchers/closing-a-protocol.html> for complete details.

APPENDIX C

ORGANIZATION IRB STUDY INFORMATION SHEET

University of California, Irvine
 Study Information Sheet
 Implementing Evidence-Based Practices for Interdisciplinary Rounding: Performance
 Improvement Project

Lead Researcher

Brooke Baldwin-Rodriguez, Nurse Manager, Burn Unit

Department of Critical Care

714-456-5829, bbaldwin@uci.edu

Faculty Sponsor

Dr. Victor Joe, Director, Burn Services

Department of Trauma/Critical Care/Burn Surgery

714-456-5840, vcjoe@uci.edu

Other Researchers

Denise Ildefonso, BSN, RN, CCRN, CWON

Maurice Espinoza, MSN, CNS, RN, CCRN

Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN

- You are being asked to participate in a research study to improve the structures and processes for the multidisciplinary team patient care rounding for the burn service at UC Irvine Medical Center.
- You are eligible to participate in this study if you at least 18 years of age or older, provide care for patients on the burn service, and participate in weekly interdisciplinary rounds.
- The research procedures involve observations and notations about the patient care rounds. And voluntarily providing feedback on the interdisciplinary rounding process.
- Possible risks/discomforts associated with the study may include feeling uncomfortable giving input in a group setting.
- There are no direct benefits from participation in the study. However, this study may help to improve interdisciplinary rounds for the burn service by ensuring that evidence-based practices for patient care rounding are included in the teams rounding structures and processes.
- You will not be compensated for your participation in this research study.
- All research data collected will be stored securely and confidentially in a locked cabinet in the office of the nurse manager. No identifiable data will be collected for this study.
- The research team, authorized UCI personnel, Brooke Baldwin-Rodriguez, Victor Joe, Denise Ildefonso, Maurice Espinoza, and Penny Weismuller may have access to the study records to protect subjects' safety and welfare. Any information derived from this research project that personally identifies you will not be voluntarily released or disclosed by these entities without your separate consent, except as specifically required by law.

UCI IRB Registered: 09-23 | APP # 9220 | HS# 2015-2193 1 of 2

UCI IRB USE ONLY: Info Sheet v. May 2011

- If you have any comments, concerns, or questions regarding the conduct of this research please contact the researchers listed at the top of this form.
- Please contact UCI's Office of Research by phone, (949) 824-6662, by e-mail at IRB@research.uci.edu or at 5171 California Avenue, Suite 150, Irvine, CA 92697 if you are unable to reach the researchers listed at the top of the form and have general questions; have concerns or complaints about the research; have questions about your rights as a research subject; or have general comments or suggestions.
- Participation in this study is voluntary. There is no cost to you for participating. You may choose to skip a question or a study procedure. You may refuse to participate or discontinue your involvement at any time without penalty. You are free to withdraw from this study at any time. If you decide to withdraw from this study you should notify the research team immediately.

UCI IRB Registered: 09-23 | APP # 9220 | HS# 2015-2193 2 of 2

APPENDIX D**CSUF IRB APPROVAL****IRB APPROVAL HSR-15-0426**

Del Rio, Natalie <ndelrio@exchange.fullerton.edu> Fri, Oct 16, 2015 at 2:59 PM
To: "brookebaldwin@csu.fullerton.edu" <brookebaldwin@csu.fullerton.edu>,
"Weismuller, Penny" <pweismuller@exchange.fullerton.edu>

Re: Implementing Evidence-Based Practices for Interdisciplinary Rounding:
Performance Improvement Project

Brooke Baldwin-Rodriguez,

The application you submitted to the IRB office has been initially reviewed and has been approved. Please pick up the approval letter and consent form if applicable from **your faculty advisor, Dr. Penny Weismuller**. It will be sent via campus mail to the department office (**EC-190**). If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me.

Natalie Del Río
Research Compliance, McCarthy Hall-103
California State University Fullerton
Tel: 657-278-7640 / Fax: 657-278-7238

APPENDIX E

PROJECT SUMMARY DOCUMENT

This document is the handout used for summarizing the performance improvement project to the burn team.

Implementing Evidence-Based Practices for Patient Care Rounding: A Performance Improvement Project

Presented by: Brooke Baldwin-Rodriguez

Nurse Manager, Burn Unit

July 14, 2015

Local Context: Eight-bed inpatient burn unit with an average daily census of 10. Adult and pediatric patient with burns and other complex skin conditions. Current patient care rounding include weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds on Monday with approximately 25 disciplines considered part of the team and approximately 15 Health care providers present during weekly patient care rounding

Problem: Structures and process of weekly multidisciplinary rounds are based on a two-decades old practice and there is lack of evidence-based practices integrated into the weekly interdisciplinary rounds

Project Purpose: To implement evidence-based practices for patient care rounding for weekly interdisciplinary rounds for an in-patient adult and pediatric burn service

Review of the Literature: Literature and evidence gathered organized into three main categories, which were reviewed for this project:

1. Patient Care Rounding
2. Patient & Family Centered Care
3. Interprofessional Collaboration

Patient Care Rounding (PCR): A process of two or more disciplines coming together at regular intervals for the purpose of interdisciplinary planning of patient care. A total of 13 evidence-informed practices for patient care rounds were identified with the strongest evidence including: standardized structure and time, clear role delineation, goal oriented approach, checklist (informational tool). Missing/Limited in the Literature are standardized and core elements for informational tools (checklists) and how to direct measure improvements in interdisciplinary rounds. Information Technology poses the following challenges for documenting patient care rounds in the medical record:

- Built for single-user interface
- Does not support collaborative/shared decision making
- Does not support multiuser interfaces
- Goal: Full implementation of the electronic health record

Interprofessional Collaboration (IPC): Is the culmination of teamwork, collaboration, and communication (see Figure 5). Effective teamwork and collaboration is represented by shared goals, shared decision-making, shared responsibility, and shared problem solving. Effective communication is represented by accurate, comprehensible, reliable, culturally competent, repeatable, standardized, open, timely, and with a common set of rules. Challenges and barriers to interprofessional collaboration can be seen in Table 9.

Figure 5. Elements of Effective Interprofessional Collaboration.

Table 9

Challenges and Barriers to Interprofessional Collaboration

Challenges and Barriers to Interprofessional Collaboration	
Teamwork & Collaboration	Communication
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender differences • Discipline-specific training • Unequal status • Role confusion • Varying levels of commitment to the group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asynchronous communication • Silence • Speaking frequently • Argumentative • Lack of team-centered approach

Patient-and-Family Centered Care (PFCC): Patient-and-family centered care represents the ideal in delivering safe patient care. The goal is for patients and families participate in planning of patient care (see Figure 6). Challenges and barriers to patient-and-family centered care are outlined in Table 10.

Figure 6. Elements of Patient-and-Family Centered Care.

Table 10

Challenges and Barriers to Patient and Family Centered Care

Challenges and Barriers to Patient and Family Centered Care	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of medical jargon • Unilateral rather than bilateral conversations • Information sharing from health care team rather than shared decision making • Healthcare provider centric timing of rounds • Lack of time and workload pressures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concerns about privacy of confidentiality • Health care provider communication may be constrained • Resident teaching may be decreased

Achieving the goal of evidence-based patient care rounds includes a team approach to decision making regarding how to incorporate evidence regarding patient care rounds, interprofessional collaboration, and patient-and-family centered care into the weekly interdisciplinary patient care rounds. The plan for implementation includes:

- Review of best practices for patient care rounds (see Table 11)
- Use of team meetings, patient care rounding, standardized tools, and team centered communication were considered (see Table 12)
- The project included five phases (see Figure 7)
- Outcome measures (see Table 13)
- Appreciative inquiry for team feedback (see Figure 8)

Table 11

Review of Best PCR Practices

Best Practice	Strength of Recommendation ^a (JAMA GRADE ^b)
Implement multidisciplinary rounds (including at least a medical doctor, registered nurse, and pharmacist)	Strong—definitely do it (↑↑A)
Standardize location, time, and team composition	Strong—definitely do it (↑↑B)
Define explicit roles for each HCP participating on rounds	Strong—definitely do it (↑↑B)
Develop and implement structured tool (best practices checklist)	Strong—definitely do it (↑↑B)
Reduce nonessential time wasting activities	Strong—definitely do it (↑↑B)
Minimize unnecessary interruptions	Strong—definitely do it (↑↑C)
Focus discussions on development of daily goals and document all discussed goals in health record	Strong—definitely do it (↑↑C)
Conduct discussions at bedside to promote patient-centeredness	Weak—probably do it (↑?A)
Conduct discussions in conference room to promote efficiency and communication	Weak—probably do it (↑?C)
Establish open collaborative discussion environment	Weak—probably do it (↑?C)
Ensure clear visibility between all HCP	Weak—probably do it (↑?D)
Empower HCP to promote team-based approach to discussions	Weak—probably do it (↑?D)
Produce visual presentation of patient information	No specific recommendation (??D)

GRADE = Grades of Recommendation Assessment, Development, and Evaluation, HCP = healthcare provider.

^aBased on the GRADE system, evaluating the efficacy of the intervention, balance between desirable and undesirable effects, costs (resource allocation), and quality of evidence (detailed summary of grading available on request).

^b↑↑ = strong recommendation, ↑? = weak recommendation, ?? = no recommendation. Quality of evidence: A = very strong, B = strong, C = moderate, D = weak. Table sorted by strength of recommendation.

Table 12

Planned Methods for Implementing Effective Elements of Interprofessional Collaboration

Element of IPC	Planned Method
Interprofessional Meetings	Monthly Burn Team PI Meeting
Interprofessional Rounding	Weekly Monday Patient Care Rounds
Standardized Informational Tool	Interdisciplinary informational rounding tool
Shared Decision Making	Team based decision making for implementation of patient care rounds
Communication using a team-centered approach	Team-Centered Communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating the action the team will take • Suggest a team action • Asking about a team action

Figure 7. Project Phases.

Table 13

Outcome Measure Monitoring Plan

Outcome Measures		Monitoring Plan
Clinical	Decreased length of stay (LOS)	Monitoring for LOS for fiscal year 2014, 2015 & 2016
	Increased in near miss error reporting	Baseline will be 1 year prior to implementation of pilot date
	Decrease errors	Baseline will be 1 year prior to implementation of pilot date
Patient and Family Satisfaction	Maintain or increase patient satisfaction scores	Press G
Care Provider Satisfaction		

Figure 8. Appreciative Inquiry Feedback Methodology.

APPENDIX F

13 EVIDENCE-INFORMED PRACTICES SUMMARY

Table 14

13 Evidence-Informed Practices for Patient Care Rounds

1	Implement multidisciplinary rounds (including at least a medical doctor, registered nurse, and pharmacist)	
2	Standardized location, time, and team composition	
3	Define explicit roles for each health care provider participating on rounds	Strongly Recommended – definitely do it
4	Develop and implement structured tool (best practice checklist)	
5	Reduce nonessential time wasting activities	
6	Minimize unnecessary interruptions	
7	Focus discussions on development of daily goals and document all discussed goals in health record	
8	Conduct discussions at bedside to promote patient-centeredness	
9	Conduct discussions in conference room to promote efficiency and communication	
10	Establish open collaborative discussion environment	Weak – probably do it
11	Ensure clear visibility between all healthcare providers	
12	Empower healthcare providers to promote team-based approach to discussions	
13	Produce visual presentation of patient information	No specific Recommendation
<i>Do we implement, how do we implement, what does this look like for the burn team?</i>		
1	Implement multidisciplinary rounds (including at least a medical doctor, registered nurse, and pharmacist)	
2	Standardized location, time, and team composition	
3	Define explicit roles for each health care provider participating on rounds	
4	Develop and implement structured tool (best practice checklist)	
5	Reduce nonessential time wasting activities	
6	Minimize unnecessary interruptions	
7	Focus discussions on development of daily goals and document all discussed goals in health record	
8	Conduct discussions at bedside to promote patient-centeredness	
9	Conduct discussions in conference room to promote efficiency and communication	
10	Establish open collaborative discussion environment	
11	Ensure clear visibility between all healthcare providers	
12	Empower healthcare providers to promote team-based approach to discussions	
13	Produce visual presentation of patient information	

APPENDIX G

ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES: MODIFIED SWOT ANALYSIS

Defining Roles and Responsibilities for Burn Team Members				
	Mandatory at Rounds	Optional	Strengths of the Role	Opportunities to Highlight the Role Better in Weekly Interdisciplinary Rounds
Your Role:				
Assistant Burn Coordinator				
Burn Program Manager				
Burn Trauma Administrative Analyst				
Case Manager				
Child Life Specialist				
Clinical Nurse Specialist				
Dietician				
Infection Control Practitioner				
Nurse Educator				
Nurse Manager/Assistant Nurse Manager				

Defining Roles and Responsibilities for Burn Team Members					
		Mandatory at Rounds	Optional	Strengths of the Role	Opportunities to Highlight the Role Better in Weekly Interdisciplinary Rounds
Nursing	Bedside				
	Wound Care				
	PCC/CN IV				
Occupational Therapy					
Palliative Care					
Pediatric Intensivist					
Pharmacist					
Physical Therapy					
Physician					
Physician Assistant					
Psychologist					
Resident Physician					
Respiratory Therapy					
Social Worker					
Speech Therapist					

APPENDIX H

PROPOSED ELEMENTS FOR THE INFORMATIONAL TOOL

Interdisciplinary Care Plan

Patient Name:

Room:

Diagnosis:

Current LOS (days)

Readmission Risk Score:

Discharge Plan:

- Anticipated discharge date:
- Location:
- Issues to address for discharge
 - Physiologic:
 - Psychosocial:
 - Appropriateness of Soar Supporter

Patient/Family top priorities

- What have the patient and/or family communicated as top priorities?

Safety

- What is the patients' greatest safety risk?

Mediations

- Concerns about current medications?
- New medications:

Code Status:

- Advance Directive: Yes/No, Status:

Mobility

Nutrition

Tubes/Lines/Drains

Pain management

Skin

Presence of Ventilator:

- SAT/SBT
- Plan for extubation

Developmental Issues/Concerns/Plan

Psychosocial

- Main concerns
- Appropriate for SOAR supporter, if yes, plan for contacting

Consults needed:

Gaps in Care: Are we missing anything?

Communication with Family

What will we communicate to the patient/family based on rounds?

APPENDIX I
INFORMATIONAL TOOL: PILOT VERSION

Patient Story

- Patient concerns while in the hospital
- Most important thing that will make a difference in the patient stay
- Personal treatment goal
- What do you know about your treatment plan
- How would you parents/others like to participate in your care
- What questions/concerns do you/child have about you/your child's health or care
- Other Information

Patient Family Priorities

- Patient Family Priorities

Discharge Information

- Hospital days
- Anticipated discharge date
- Discharge Destination
- Other Needs

Issues/barrier to discharge/progress of care

- Concerns about current medications
- Anticipated discharge medications

Goals/Interventions

- Safety
- Cognitive Communication
- Mobility
- Splinting
- Nutrition
- GI/GU
- Tubes/Lines/Drains
- Pain Management
- Skin/Wound
- Respiratory
- Other
- Psychosocial
 - Developmental
 - Knowledge
 - Issues/Support System
 - Appropriateness for SOAR Supporter

Patient Barriers/Care Concerns

- Patient Barriers: family
- Patient Care Concerns
- End of Life

Discharge Plan/Progress of Care Comments

- Plan for Surgery
- Discharge Plan/Progress of Care Comments

Team Members Present

APPENDIX J

INPUT AND FEEDBACK FROM BURN TEAM MEMBERS

Table 15. *Input and Feedback from Burn Team Members*

Feedback Regarding Standardized Rounding Time and Rounding Location Preferences			Recommendations
Standardized Time	Does the starting time of rounds at 2:30 impact your day in a negative way? If yes, what would be a better time to start weekly interdisciplinary rounds?	No (13)	Yes (2)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is a great time it is consistent time and it is late enough to see all patients before the meeting Labs come back by 2:30 for dietary contributions 	Better start time is 1:30 8:30. 1pm, 1:30pm, or 3:30 to allow me to see other patients
What is your preference of location?	<p>A) Conduct discussions gathered in the nurses station</p> <p>B) Conduct discussion outside of each patient room with the door closed</p> <p>C) Conduct discussions outside of each patient room and include the patient and/or family</p> <p>D) Conduct</p>	<p>A = (3) B = (5) C = (3) D = (6)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patient and family should be included in discussion and I think it might make them feel more at ease that such a large team is involved in their care Include goals of the patient and family in the discussion I like the efficiency of being in a conference room but I see the value of involving the patient and family When it is outside the patient room with the door closed the patients can often hear anyway and doesn't make it more patient focused to me- easier for RN to be there A conference room setting may hold attention of the team 	<p>Conducting the patient care rounds in a conference room setting seems the most frequently preferred preference. Recommend trialing the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Include the patient and family priorities and elements of the patient story from the bedside RN into the discussion during the patient care rounds 2-week (1 week with Dr. Joe, 1 week with Dr. Bernal) trial of rounding in the hallway and outside of the

	<p>discussions in a conference room like setting</p>	<p>better. I don't see much benefit in standing in the hallway unless it is decided that the patient/family should be involved. When considering involving patient/family I think it may prolongs rounds because patient/family may not understand the structure and it could be difficult to keep non-burn team members succinct and on topic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I think to be more family centered, care focused including families is always optimal, but other facilities do it during interdisciplinary rounds with physicians. During interdisciplinary rounds it would be too hard in front of families to discuss psychosocial issues • Option D may discourage bedside RN input, which is a negative, but it would increase patient privacy • Ideally I think doing twice with C & D would be great, but requires an extra rounds 	<p>patient room and/or at the nurses station</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2-week (1 week with Dr. Joe, 1 week with Dr. Bernal) trial of patient care rounding in the burn unit workroom • Obtain feedback for each two-week trial
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APPENDIX K

STRUCTURED OBSERVATIONAL TOOL

Patient Care Rounds Observation Tool			
Date of PCRs: _____ Start time: _____ End time: _____			
Observation Guide	Yes	No	Comments
Did patient care rounds start on time?			
Did all essential team members arrive on time?			
Team member roles are clearly understood			
The structured interdisciplinary rounding tool followed or all patient discussions.			
Were non-essential time wasting activities noted?			
Were interruptions noted during rounds?			
Were patient-and-family top priorities recorded on the information tool?			
Was at least one goal identified based on patient-and-family input and documented on the patient care rounding tool?			
Were rounds conducted in an open and collaborative forum?			
Was a team-based approach to communication used ('we' will do)?			
Do team members appear to pay attention to and respect one another?			
Were there any conflicts (if yes, please answer next question)?			
Were conflicts resolved in a collaborative manner?			
Were any team members disruptive during rounds?			

APPENDIX L
APPRECIATIVE INQUIRY 4-D MODEL

Figure 9. Appreciative Inquiry 4-D Model.

Appreciative Inquiry Guide for Debriefing Post-Rounding Experience	
Discover	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were the strengths of patient care rounds today? • What do you value most about the patient care rounding experience?
Dream	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What positive impact will the patient care rounds have on patients and families • What positive impact will the patient care rounds have on the health care team
Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is there anything that will make patient care rounds even better?
Destiny	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do we work to sustain the patient care rounding practices?

APPENDIX M

ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES: FINAL

Burn Team Roles and Responsibilities		
	Presence at Weekly Patient Care Rounds	Main focus for Role on the Burn Team
Assistant Burn Coordinator	Optional	Main role for burn team is tracking complications, quality of care issues, delays in transfer, and opportunities for burn prevention education and burn survivor programs. Gathers data needed for burn verification process.
Burn Program Manager	Optional	Main role for burn team is tracking complications, quality of care issues, delays in transfer, and opportunities for burn prevention education and burn survivor programs. Gathers data needed for burn verification process. Also provides: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-profit patient assistance • Community/fire department involvement • Opportunities for burn prevention education • Oversight of burn survivor programs • Oversight of quality of care issues with a referring hospital
Burn Trauma Administrative Analyst	Optional	Provided statistical data for the burn program
Case Manager	Mandatory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early discharge planning • Provides information for patient disposition needs • Insurance issues • Placement of patients after discharge • Identification of barriers to discharge • Facilitates discharges, home health referrals, transfers to other facilities
Child Life Specialist	Mandatory for pediatric patients, Optional for needs of children of critically ill adult patients	Addresses the needs of the following populations: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Pediatric patients 0-17 year 2) Assistance with children of adult patients as needed Participates in the following activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assesses and Evaluates developmental needs • Family and patient coping • Assesses patient and family understanding of diagnosis and treatment plan

Burn Team Roles and Responsibilities			
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitates discharge planning for returning to school Facilitates developmental needs post-discharge Actively engages parents for child's coping with plan of care for very young patients Provides guidance for health care providers for age-appropriate activities and developmental needs of patients Provides assistance with procedures
Clinical Nurse Specialist		Optional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resource on nursing practice/equipment Clarifies policies/procedures Provides updates pertaining to patient care as needed
Dietician		Mandatory	Provides information regarding nutritional status of patient. Clarifies dietary orders, nutritional status as noted by lab values and calorie intake.
Infection Control Practitioner		Optional	Provides reminders and brings awareness to situations in the unit regarding prevention of infections and colonization/infection clusters
Nurse Educator		Optional	To determine educational needs of staff
Nurse Manager/Assistant Nurse Manager		Mandatory	Coordination of care especially when RN specific issues arise for day-to-day care. Clarifies recommendations from the team members. Can provide solutions and remove barriers when nursing/unit issues are discovered. To understand what is going on with all patients.
Nursing	Bedside	Mandatory	<p>Gives updates about patient's current status regarding response to treatment plan and needed nursing interventions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provides input on goal attainment Identifies barriers to whether care plan goals have been met
	Wound Care	Optional	Provides the daily burn/wound care for patients on the burn service. This role is rotate among the burn unit RNs
	PCC/CN IV	Mandatory	Has oversight of unit operations including staffing, patient placement and quality of care for the burn unit. Clarifies changes in patient care plans and assists with consistency of information transferred shift-to-shift
Occupational Therapy		Mandatory	Provides assessment, evaluation and treatment for improving activities of daily living and progression of therapy. Defines patient limitations.
Palliative Care		Optional	Helps provide guidance on pain management and end-of-life issues
Pediatric Intensivist		Mandatory when pediatric patients present	Resource for pediatric patient, especially for critical care issues and non-burn related care issues. Coordinates care for pediatric patients

Burn Team Roles and Responsibilities		
Pharmacist	Mandatory, also need pediatric pharmacist if there are pediatric patients	Provides oversight of medication management.
Physical Therapy	Mandatory	Progression of therapy, mobility, suggests assistive devices, tolerance to activity, and pain during therapy. Clarifies limitations and responsiveness to treatment plans.
Physician	Mandatory	Develops the medical plan of care in consideration of input from all disciplines.
Physician Assistant	Mandatory	Has in-depth knowledge of patients medical plan of care, writes orders during patient care rounds, and clarifies orders and updates orders as appropriate.
Psychologist	Mandatory	Provides assessment, evaluation and treatment of psychosocial needs for the patients.
Resident Physician	Mandatory	Presents patient and provides information regarding the medical plan of care
Respiratory Therapy	Optional, but optimally present for intubated patients or patient with respiratory needs	Updates team on respiratory status, progression and plan for extubation
Social Worker	Mandatory	Provides information and support regarding family and patient psychosocial needs. Addresses financial and support needs for patients and families.
Speech Therapist	Optional	May be needed to give input on swallow evaluations, speech issues, and cognitive evaluations.
Unit Secretary	Mandatory	Provides education to patients and families each Monday regarding the patient care rounds. Discusses the time of rounding and facilitates minimizing interruptions from phone and doors during rounds.

APPENDIX N

PILOT DESIGN ELEMENTS

The interdisciplinary burn team is reviewing evidence-based practices for implementation into the weekly burn interdisciplinary weekly patient care rounds. A systematic review published by Lane et al. (2013), identified 13-evidence practices for patient care rounds. Our team is reviewing our practices in relations to the 13-evidence based practices. Below is a summary of the practices and a description about how the practice will be implemented for patients on the burn service.

Table 16. *Pilot Design Elements*

Evidence-Informed Practice		UC Irvine Burn Center Approach	
Strongly Recommended	Implement multidisciplinary rounds (including at least a medical doctor, registered nurse, and pharmacist)	Patient care rounds are implemented. Frequency of rounds is weekly on Mondays, starting at 2:30pm. A modified version of the interdisciplinary rounds occurs on Thursday from 11am to Noon.	
	Standardized location, time, and team composition	Current Process	Future State
		<u>Monday</u> Location: Dependent on attending (a) conducted at each nurses station, side A or side B or (b) conducted outside of each patients room with the door closed Time: 2:30 – approximately 3:30 Team Composition: Currently all burn team members are invited, currently working on a document for roles and responsibilities which also outlines who is mandatory at rounds and which roles are optional	<u>Monday</u> Location: Survey of members of the burn team (see attached results) Time: 2:30 – approximately 3:30 Team Composition: See Roles and Responsibility Document
<u>Thursday</u> Location: Burn Workroom Time: 11 am - Noon Team Composition: physician, nurses,	<u>Thursday</u> Location: Burn Workroom Time: 11 am - Noon Team Composition: physician,		

		social worker, case managers	nurses, social worker, case managers (others TBD)
	Define explicit roles for each health care provider participating on rounds	See Roles and Responsibilities Document	
	Develop and implement structured tool (best practice checklist)	See Screen Shots of the electronic document	
	Reduce nonessential time wasting activities	Expected to be addressed with the structured implementation tool. Monitoring via Observations will be done to monitor this aspect during rounds, Observation Tool for Evaluation of Patient Care Rounds (Appendix K)	
	Minimize unnecessary interruptions	Need to identify the most frequent types of interruptions to better address this element	
	Focus discussions on development of goals and document all discussed goals in health record	TBD	
Weak – Probably Do It	Conduct discussions at bedside to promote patient-centeredness	See attached document	
	Conduct discussions in conference room to promote efficiency and communication	See attached document	
	Establish open collaborative discussion environment	Observation Tool for Evaluation of Patient Care Rounds	
	Ensure clear visibility between all healthcare providers	Need to discuss	
	Empower healthcare providers to promote team-based approach to discussions	Need to discuss	
No Recommendation	Produce visual presentation of patient information	Need to discuss	

APPENDIX O

OBSERVATIONS AND APPRECIATIVE INQUIRY NOTES

Patient Care Rounds Observation Tool			
Date of PCRs: <u> 10/19/15 </u> Start time: <u> 2:35 </u> End time: <u> 3:30 </u>			
Attending physician A. Rounds covered 4 patients while standing around nursing station on Side A of unit; second group of 4 patients discussed while team standing around nurses station of Side B of unit.			
Observation Guide	Yes	No	Comments
Did patient care rounds start on time?		X	Started within 5 minutes of scheduled time; within 5 minutes
Did all essential team members arrive on time?		X	Within 5 minutes of scheduled time; within 5 minutes
Team member roles are clearly understood	X		
The structured interdisciplinary rounding tool followed or all patient discussions.		X	No discussion of patients plan; no discussion of patient's plan
Were non-essential time wasting activities noted?	X		Question about burn program aspects – are these necessary during rounds? When team moved from side A to side B team seemed to lose focus briefly with an increase in side conversations
Were interruptions noted during rounds?	X		People coming in through the unit doors (lift team, burn & wound team, & side conversations); intercom to let visitors in x4; side conversations x2 that were not patient focused; x2 side conversations that were patient focused Outside noise was distracting – doors, carts, etc. difficult to hear soft spoken team members

Were patient-and-family top priorities recorded on the information tool?		X	Old tool used – patient and family priorities not part of tool; old tool used that is not patient focused
Was at least one goal identified based on patient-and-family input and documented on the patient care rounding tool?		X	DC dates – patients specific goals hard to identify; old tool used that is not patient focused
Were rounds conducted in an open and collaborative forum?	X		
Was a team-based approach to communication used ('we' will do)?	X		“our” and “we” used
Do team members appear to pay attention to and respect one another?	X		
Were there any conflicts (if yes, please answer next question)?		X	
Were conflicts resolved in a collaborative manner?			
Were any team members disruptive during rounds?		X	
<p>1. Discover:</p> <p>a. What were the strengths of patient care rounds today? Able to finish by 3:30pm</p> <p>b. What do you value most about the patient care rounding experience? The burn team coming together and discussing patients.</p> <p>2. Dream</p> <p>a. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on patients and families?</p> <p>b. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on the healthcare team?</p>			<p>3. Design</p> <p>a. Is there anything that could make patient care rounds even better?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doorbell for visitors to enter unit disruptive • Can all pediatric patients be rounded on first – can we get the pediatric pharmacist to join rounds • Be sure to include patient and family goals • Introduction to patient needs to be a short synopsis • Would like to add patients last surgery and next expected surgery during rounds <p>4. Destiny: How do we work to sustain patient care rounding practices?</p>

Patient Care Rounds Observation Tool

Date of PCRs: 10/26/15 Start time: 2:40 End time: 3:30

Attending B. Rounds started on side A of the unit and then moved room to room. Each patient care rounding episode occurred outside of the door of the patient room.

Observation Guide	Yes	No	Comments
Did patient care rounds start on time?		X	Physician delayed
Did all essential team members arrive on time?		X	Pharmacist, identified as a mandatory member not present.
Team member roles are clearly understood	X		
The structured interdisciplinary rounding tool followed or all patient discussions.		X	Old tool based on disciplines; semi-structured
Were non-essential time-wasting activities noted?	X		Pharmacist not at rounds – time spent trying to find a pharmacist to participate in rounds; distractions of team members
Were interruptions noted during rounds?	X		Housekeeper refilling cleaning cart in the middle of rounds was disruptive; side conversations x 3
Were patient-and-family top priorities recorded on the information tool?		X	Discussed sleeping regarding one patient, but that was all the patient focused discussion
Was at least one goal identified based on patient-and-family input and documented on the patient care rounding tool?		X	New tool still not implemented
Were rounds conducted in an open and collaborative forum?	X		Input from each team member
Was a team-based approach to communication used ('we' will do)?	X		

Do team members appear to pay attention to and respect one another?	X				
Were there any conflicts (if yes, please answer next question)?		X			
Were conflicts resolved in a collaborative manner?	X				
Were any team members disruptive during rounds?	X		Side conversations but improved since last week		
<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <p>1. Discover:</p> <p>a. What were the strengths of patient care rounds today? Use of humor during rounds; make sure we don't get rid of humor</p> <p>b. What do you value most about the patient care rounding experience? Brings all team members together</p> <p>2. Dream</p> <p>a. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on patients and families?</p> <p>b. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on the healthcare team?</p> </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <p>1. Design</p> <p>a. Is there anything that could make patient care rounds even better?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different order of topics for the structured tool • Keep on topic • Focused brief discussion <p>2. Destiny</p> <p>a. How do we work to sustain patient care rounding practices?</p> <p>i. Continue to give feedback</p> </td> </tr> </table>				<p>1. Discover:</p> <p>a. What were the strengths of patient care rounds today? Use of humor during rounds; make sure we don't get rid of humor</p> <p>b. What do you value most about the patient care rounding experience? Brings all team members together</p> <p>2. Dream</p> <p>a. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on patients and families?</p> <p>b. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on the healthcare team?</p>	<p>1. Design</p> <p>a. Is there anything that could make patient care rounds even better?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different order of topics for the structured tool • Keep on topic • Focused brief discussion <p>2. Destiny</p> <p>a. How do we work to sustain patient care rounding practices?</p> <p>i. Continue to give feedback</p>
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Patient Care Rounds Observation Tool			
Date of PCRs: ____11/2/15____ Start time: __2:40____ End time: ____3:45____			
Attending physician B: Conference room setting			
Observation Guide	Yes	No	Comments
Did patient care rounds start on time?		X	Attending Physician delayed
Did all essential team members arrive on time?	X		
Team member roles are clearly understood	X		Multiple team members chiming in off topic
The structured interdisciplinary rounding tool followed or all patient discussions.		X	In part. First time trying the tool and not followed for first few patients
Were non-essential time-wasting activities noted?	X		Not staying on topic of discussion. In depth information provided vs. brief summary of patient care needs.
Were interruptions noted during rounds?	X		Phone calls into workroom
Were patient-and-family top priorities recorded on the information tool?	X		On new informational tool
Was at least one goal identified based on patient-and-family input and documented on the patient care rounding tool?	X		Yes on new informational tool
Were rounds conducted in an open and collaborative forum?	X		Input from each team member
Was a team-based approach to communication used ('we' will do)?	X		

Do team members appear to pay attention to and respect one another?	X		
Were there any conflicts (if yes, please answer next question)?		X	
Were conflicts resolved in a collaborative manner?	NA	NA	
Were any team members disruptive during rounds?		X	
<p>1. Discover:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. What were the strengths of patient care rounds today? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less interruptions b. What do you value most about the patient care rounding experience? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visualization of photos <p>2. Dream</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on patients and families? Including the patient story b. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on the healthcare team? <p>3. Design</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Is there anything that could make patient care rounds even better? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different order of topics for the structured tool • Keep on topic • Focused brief discussion <p>4. Destiny</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. How do we work to sustain patient care rounding practices? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Continue to give feedback 			

Patient Care Rounds Observation Tool

Date of PCRs: ____11/9/15_____ Start time: __1433_____ End time: ____1510_____

Attending physician A. Conference Room Setting

Observation Guide	Yes	No	Comments
Did patient care rounds start on time?	X		
Did all essential team members arrive on time?	X		
Team member roles are clearly understood	X		
The structured interdisciplinary rounding tool followed or all patient discussions.	X		
Were non-essential time-wasting activities noted?	X	X	Nurse PCC confused as to her role stated she was unaware of what was expected (1444) – another RN took over computer charting
Were interruptions noted during rounds?	X		
Were patient-and-family top priorities recorded on the information tool?	X		
Was at least one goal identified based on patient-and-family input and documented on the patient care rounding tool?	X		
Were rounds conducted in an open and collaborative forum?	X		
Was a team-based approach to communication used ('we' will do)?	X		

Do team members appear to pay attention to and respect one another?	X		
Were there any conflicts (if yes, please answer next question)?	X		
Were conflicts resolved in a collaborative manner?	X		
Were any team members disruptive during rounds?		X	
<p>1. Discover:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. What were the strengths of patient care rounds today? b. What do you value most about the patient care rounding experience? <p>2. Dream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on patients and families? Including the patient story b. What positive impact will patient care rounds have on the healthcare team? <p>3. Design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Is there anything that could make patient care rounds even better? <p>4. Destiny</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. How do we work to sustain patient care rounding practices? 			

APPENDIX P

STRUCTURED NOTE OUTPUT

<u>Discharge Information:</u>	
• Hospital Days	4
• Anticipated Discharge Date	12-21-2015
<u>Goals/Interventions:</u>	
<u>Safety:</u>	
• Last Week's Goal/Interventions	Fall risk. Institute fall precaution.
<u>Cognitive/Communication:</u>	
• Last Week's Goal/Interventions	concern about mental status. Recommend a cognitive/speech evaluation.
<u>Mobility:</u>	
• Last Week's Goal/Interventions	Limited due to pain.
<u>Nutrition:</u>	
• Last Week's Goal/Interventions	1. vitamin D > 30 ng/dl 2. Meet >75% of her nutritional needs via po intake 3. Prealbumin >17 mg/dl 4. Meet 100% of her nutritional needs via enteral feeding alone, or combo of po + TF
<u>Pain Management:</u>	
• Last Week's Goal/Interventions	Will establish a pain management protocol. Will evaluate over next 24 hours. May consult palliative is unable to control pain.
<u>Skin/Wound:</u>	
• Last Week's Goal/Interventions	Daily wound care. Consulting dermatology, will start on IVIG
<u>Other:</u>	
• Last Week's Goal/Interventions	dysphagia eval completed 11/9. Rec: continue Mech Soft diet, Thin liquids. Main has mild oral dysphagia due to dryness/sores. Advance as tolerated. ST signing off, no skilled ST needs at this time. Goal for patient to be able to feed herself, moderate assistance. Patient will participate in range of motion exercises to prep for ADLs
<u>Discharge Plan/Progress of Care Comments:</u>	
• Discharge Plan/Progress of Care Comments:	Improve pain control.
• Team Members Present	attending; resident; psychologist; physician assistant; case management; nursing; social work

Figure 10. Structured Electronic Note Output.

APPENDIX Q

WEEKLY PATIENT CARE ROUNDS CHECKLIST

Weekly Interdisciplinary Patient Care Rounds Checklist <i>To be completed by the Charge Nurse and Unit Secretary Every Monday</i>		
Task		Responsible Person
0830	Validate that the Interdisciplinary Plan of Care Rounds structured note was Initiated by the Night Shift RN and the Patient Story complete. If not complete instruct the day shift bedside RN to complete the Patient Story.	Charge Nurse
0830	Review list of patients on burn service and determine if there are any pediatric patients (ages 13 and below) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If there are pediatric patient page the following: child life specialist, pediatric pharmacist, pediatric intensivist 	Unit Secretary or Charge Nurse
0830	Check if regularly scheduled case manager, social worker, and adult pharmacists are working. If there is a covering person please page to remind about the 2:30 rounds start time	Unit Secretary or Charge Nurse
1400	Set up burn unit workroom for rounds: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workstation of Wheels to display patient photos • Laptop & projector to display burn interdisciplinary plan of care structured note 	Unit Secretary

APPENDIX R

INFORMATIONAL TOOL CHANGES SUBMITTED

Patient Story

- Patient concerns while in the hospital
- Most important thing that will make a difference in the patient stay
- Personal treatment goal
- What do you know about your treatment plan
- How would you parents/others like to participate in care
- What questions/concerns do you/child have about you/your child's health or care
- Other Information

Discharge Plan

- Hospital days
- Anticipated discharge date
- Plan for Surgery
- Discharge Destination
- Other Needs

Goals/Interventions

- Safety
- Medications
- Cognitive Communication
- Activities of Daily Living
- Mobility
- Splinting
- Nutrition
- GI/GU
- Tubes/Lines/Drains
- Pain Management
- Skin/Wound
- Respiratory
- Other
- Psychosocial
 - Developmental
 - Knowledge
 - Issues/Support System
 - Appropriateness for SOAR Supporter

Patient Barriers/Care Concerns

- Patient Barriers: family
- Patient Care Concerns
- End of Life

Top Priorities and Goals for the Week

Team Members Present

APPENDIX S

CURRICULUM FOR LOW-FIDELITY TEAM TRAINING

COURSE TITLE: Enhance Communication and Teamwork with Team Training

INSTRUCTOR: Brooke Baldwin-Rodriguez, MSN, RN, CCRN, NE-BC

TARGET AUDIENCE: Members of the Burn Team at UC Irvine

COURSE DESCRIPTION: Interprofessional collaboration, specifically teamwork and communication, will be enhanced through a team training simulation using concepts from TeamSTEPPS®. Team roles and responsibilities, effective team-centered communication, and promoting patient-and-family centered care will be emphasized for patient care rounding.

OBJECTIVES: Upon completion of the course, burn team members will:

1. Discriminate the roles and responsibilities of each member of the burn team
2. Demonstrate the ability to provide brief, clear, and specific information to the team
3. Use team-centered communication strategies to state the actions the team will take
4. Promote input from all members of the team
5. Demonstrate the ability to speak up and clarify information
6. Formulate at least one patient-centered goal for the plan of care

COURSE OUTLINE:

Team simulation training will be used to enhance interprofessional collaboration, teamwork and communication, among the burn team members to promote patient-centered goal setting during interdisciplinary patient care rounds.

Team Structure:

- Discriminates the roles and responsibilities of each member of the burn team

Communication:

- Demonstrate the ability to provide brief, clear, and specific information to the team
- Use team-centered communication strategies to state the specific actions that team will take

Mutual Support:

- Promote input from all members of the team
- Demonstrate the ability to speak up and clarify information

Situation Monitoring:

- Formulate at least one patient-centered goal for the plan of care

METHODOLOGY and EVALUATION

The two elements that follow presents a) the curriculum matrix for this presentation, which includes the teaching strategies and evaluation and b) the performance assessment.

Title: Team Simulation Training to Enhance Communication and Teamwork

Student Learning Outcomes/Objectives	Content/Outline	Teaching Strategies		Evaluation
		Faculty Activity	Student Activity	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discriminate the roles and responsibilities of each member of the burn team 2. Demonstrate the ability to provided brief, clear, and specific information to the team 3. Use team-centered communication strategies to state the action the team will take 4. Promote input from all members of the team 5. Demonstrate the ability to speak up and clarify information 6. Formulate at least one patient-centered goal for the plan of care 	<p>Team Structure: Burn Team Roles and Responsibilities document (see Appendix A)</p> <p>Communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the interdisciplinary plan of care document for the team to follow the patient care rounding elements (see Appendix B) • Shared responsibility and states the action the team will take using “we will do” or “let’s” phases (team centered vs. status differences) <p>Mutual Support:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essential elements of feedback (see Appendix C) • CUS tool for advocacy, assertion and mutual support (see Appendix D) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The facilitator will use the document “Burn Team Roles and Responsibilities” to review team roles and responsibilities with burn team members. 2. The facilitator will explain and demonstrate the components of the interdisciplinary plan of care and expected flow of discussion during the patient care rounds 3. The facilitator will present components of team-centered communication using statement that distinguish team-centered communication versus communication that promotes status differences among team members 4. The facilitator will present the essential elements of feedback 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The learner will provide input to the plan of care based on their scope of practice and the “Burn Team Roles and Responsibilities” document. 2. The learner will follow the prompts of the interdisciplinary plan of care during the simulation exercise 3. The learner will use “we” and “let’s”, rather the “I”, “you” 4. The learner will give feedback during simulation exercise using the essential elements for providing feedback (see Appendix C) 5. The learner will resolve a safety issue during the simulation exercise using CUS (see Appendix D) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The team score on the observation form on the component of <u>Team Structure</u> will be a score of Average or above 2. The team score on the observation form on the component of <u>Communication</u> will be a score of Average or above 3. The team score on the observation form on the component of <u>Mutual Support</u> will be a score of Average or above

	<p>Situation Monitoring: The section of “Top goals and Priorities” on the interdisciplinary plan of care will be used for patient-centered goals for the week</p>	<p>5. The facilitator will present the CUS tool for advocacy, assertion and mutual support</p> <p>6. The facilitator will provide examples of patient-centered weekly goals</p>	<p>6. The learner will formulate a patient-centered goal during the simulation exercise</p>	<p>4. The team score on the observation form on the component of <u>Situation Monitoring</u> will be a score of Average or above</p>
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Performance Assessment of Interprofessional Collaboration – Teamwork and Communication

Observer Form

Names of Participant:		Role:				
1.		1.				
2.		2.				
3.		3.				
4.		4.				
Scenario: A B C						
Observer: <i>From your perspective as a team observer, how would you describe the performance of this team? You will not describe individual performance but will focus on describing team functioning.</i>						
Skill Domains	Poor		Average		Excellent	Comments
Team Structure						
Discriminates the roles and responsibilities of each member of the burn team						
Communication						
Demonstrate the ability to provide brief, clear, and specific information to the team Use team-centered communication strategies to state the specific actions that team will take						
Mutual Support						
Promote input from all members of the team Demonstrate the ability to speak up and clarify information						
Situational Monitoring						
Formulate at least one patient-centered goal for the plan of care						

Poor: Multiple behaviors absent or not performed well; **Average:** Most behaviors present and adequately performed; **Excellent:** All behaviors present and performed well.

APPENDIX T

TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Evidence Table 1. *Patient Care Rounds (PCRs)*

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Determine content and functional requirements for standard PCR tool. Focus on plan of care content. (Collins et al., 2014)	Mixed method: quantitative and Qualitative Key variables 1) CDE related to POC & discharge plan 2) Length of rounds 3) Discussion of rounds 4) Clinicians present at rounds	10-bed ICU & intermediate care unit, academic medical center	1) NodeXL software for network visualization 2) CDEs: a) Frequency discussed b) Association with length of rounds c) Association with other CDEs	3 critical elements for PCR tool: 1) Focus of rounds discussion influenced by clinicians present 2) Length of rounds based on type of data discussed influenced the length of rounds 3) Probable universal set of empirically derived CDEs Qualitative themes: 1) enabling remote communication functionality 2) building shared and configurable views	Defined an initial set of universal and configurable CDEs (11) for a PCR tool Did not evaluate what should be discussed on rounds for effective patient care
Understanding the rounding process embedded within a Medical ICU, the purpose of rounding, and the problem of interruptions (Gupta, 2013)	Direct observations, interviews, time motion tracking	Medical ICUs, 2 teaching hospitals	Interruption = break in human activity by a source internal or external to the recipient	Total average rounding time = 11.5 minutes with 22% of time spent on tasks other than rounding Rounding decreased to 7 minutes with decreases in interruptions	Strategies to decrease interruptions has decreased PCR time

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Guidance for designing and evaluation of PCRs (Gurses & Xiao, 2006)	Systematic Review	Inclusion: all types of PCRs Exclusions: focus on teaching aspects, sign-outs, hand-offs	PCRs = regularly scheduled meetings of HCPs <u>Structural</u> = ITs <u>Process</u> = CMC & care elements <u>Outcomes</u> = COs, efficiency, patient, family & HCP SAT	<u>Structural</u> : 3 types of ITs PC tools, <u>Process</u> : 32 reported useful measures for evaluation of ITs on PCRs. Noise & interruptions = barriers <u>COs</u> : 26 different measures reported	PCRs facilitate achievement of SGs Current electronic systems do not support Collab or SDM/SGs, multiuser ITs ITs needed for information not inappropriate for MR, no discussion of operational definitions for constructs
To recommend evidence-informed practices for PCRs (Lane et al., 2013)	Systematic Review Facilitators and barriers to PCR	Inclusion: Original, peer reviewed studies, no methodological restrictions Exclusion: those focused on impact of ICU specialist, family members on rounds, focus on teaching during rounds	PCRs = regularly scheduled meetings of more than 2 health care providers	9 key rounding themes identified 13 facilitators & 9 barriers to evidence-informed practices Best practices: 7 strong, 5 weak-probably, 1 no recommendation	Strongest evidence for: standardized structure & time, best practice checklist, roles defined, goal-oriented approach Making inferences difficult due to methodological issues with studies
The impact of an electronic patient record on interactions during PCRs (Morrison et al., 2008)	Qualitative, video analysis, observation, interviews	25-bed ICU	PCRs video recorded and analyzed Observations of PCRs Interviews with PCR participants	Physical setup of PCRs with electronic patient records decrease openness of discussions, patient goals are less apparent to team Change in team formation → + changes in interactions	Awareness of disruption caused by electronic patient records should be addressed by the rounding team

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Development and testing for an interdisciplinary rounding assessment tool for measuring the quality of IDRs (Ten Have et al., 2013)	Delphi rounds of IDRs	3 ICUs; 2 hospitals	Tool development	IDR Assessment Scale: 19 quality indicators (essential or supportive), 2 domains (1) patient plan of care (2) process Inter-rater reliability = ($k = 0.85$), item score correlations = excellent ($r = 0.08-0.94$), Internal consistency acceptable ($\alpha = 0.78$)	IDR Assessment Scale can be used to assess quality of IDRs Participants were aware of being videotaped, only 3 ICUs in 2 different hospitals

Note. CDE = clinical data elements; CMC = communication; Collab = collaboration; COORDN – coordination; HCP = health care provider; HCT = healthcare team; ICU = intensive care unit or critical care unit; IT = informational tool; PC = patient centered; POC = plan of care; MD = physician; MR = medical record; PCR = patient care round; RN = registered nurses; SAT = satisfaction; SDM = shared decision making; SG = shared goals.

Evidence Table 2. *Interprofessional Collaboration (IPC)*

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Identify the professional RN CMC considered effective in HCT interactions (Apker et al., 2006)	Grounded theory with constant comparative analysis using Owen's criteria: 1) Recurrence 2) Repetition 3) Forcefulness-	348-bed tertiary hospital in the Midwest RNs, clinical nurse specialists, MDs, patient care assistants, unit clerks, unit coordinators/charge nurses Units: ICUs, general medical, general surgery	Semi-structured interview guide for individual and group interviews Focus groups -audiotaped and transcribed Shadowing of 4 nurses	4 skill sets that nurses use to convey professionalism in health care interactions: 1) Collab 2) Credibility 3) Compassion 4) COORDN 12 representative behaviors and 19 sample nonverbal and verbal techniques provided	RNs expected to have wide-ranging and complex team communication techniques; may have both positive and negative impacts for nurses RNs with professional communication skills may raise awareness of RN contribution to health care delivery
Examine prevalence, characteristics, and factors of ICU conflict (Azoulay et al., 2009)	Cross-sectional; questionnaire Key variable: conflict in the ICU; types of conflict (parties involved, source of conflict, clinical impact of severity of the conflict)	ICUs setting 1 day of	Conflict = dispute, disagreement, incompatibility, opposition, or difference of opinion involving more than on individual and related to the patients management or to interpersonal conflict	Parties involved: Source of conflict: RN-MD conflicts most common (32.6%), followed by RN-RN conflicts (27.3%), staff-relative conflict (26.6%) (1) General behaviors = most common (animosity, mistrust, poor CMC)	Job strain significantly associate with perceived conflicts
Understand medical and nursing staff perspectives on clinical decision making (Coombs, 2003)	Micro ethnographic research; theme related to power & conflict representative of one finding from a larger study	3 ICU sites	Participant observation, in-depth interviews	Key theme related to power and conflict	Traditional hierarchies within the clinical team remain

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To examine how ICU clinicians view interprofessional collaboration in the ICU (Costa et al., 2014)	Qualitative; thematic content analysis approach Interprofessional collaboration = to work with another person or group in order to achieve or do something	ICUs; 7 hospitals; practicing clinicians Clinicians: RNs, MDs, respiratory therapists, pharmacists, nurse managers, dieticians	In-person, open-ended, semi-structured interviews	Facilitators: (1) Structural facilitators: clinical protocols, checklists, daily rounds, information technology (2) Cultural facilitators: accessibility, trust, value, leadership	Used semi-structured interviews instead of ethnography, mixed ICUs used
Determine the barriers and facilitators to collab between MDs, RNs, physical therapists, physician assistants, nutritionists, & social workers (Costello & Thompson, 2015)	Descriptive qualitative research	Inpatient unit is a urban teaching hospital	9 focus groups Conducted with each discipline independently 2 question: (1) What are the perceived barriers to IPC (2) what are the facilitators to IPC	Three themes: (1) Relationships - Team members feel unsupported /disrespected by other team members - Roles not understood (2) Systems - Schedules interfere with collab practice (3) CMC - Not all members attend rounds - Telephone not an efficient form of CMC - Not all team members aware of care plan and provide conflicting info to patients	
Explores RN-MD CMC in the context of health care outcomes and provides an operational definition for RN-MD CMC (Cypress, 2011)	Concept Analysis using Rodgers' Evolutionary View of Concept Analysis RN-MD CMC, CMC, outcomes	Inclusion: original research, English language Exclusions: thesis, dissertations, news reports	<u>Attributes:</u> 9 for RN-MD CMC <u>Antecedents:</u> 5 for RN-MD CMC <u>Consequences:</u> Patient outcomes = 7 + & 7 -; Nursing outcomes = 16 + & 15 -; Physician outcomes = 3 + & 5 -	<u>Operational Definition:</u> "RN-MD CMC is the ability to transmit accurate, comprehensible, consistent, reliable, culturally competent, balanced, repeated information through a common system according to a common set of rules in an open, timely manner toward + health care outcomes"	Lack of nursing studies and qualitative studies

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Examine instances of silence and constraint in CMC in the OR (Gardezi et al., 2009)	Secondary analysis of retrospective data collection from a previous study Critical ethnography, with focus on two particular features: 1) Attention to power dynamics in silence and 2) The usefulness of critical methodology for analyzing silences	Observations in the OR suites OR Teams: 11 general surgeons 116 OR nurses 74 anesthesiologists	Observational data Observers present in the OR – field notes taken Four trained observers coded the data Three reviewers for data	Three forms of silence: 1) Absence of CMC, made evident by prior actions or CMC 2) Lack of response to a direct address by another, or responding with silence to another’s question or directive 3) Aspects of delivery that blur the lines between speech and silence, such as speaking quietly, timidly or hesitantly	Silence may be a means of exerting power over others, a reflection of relative powerlessness or a means of resisting power. Silence is important because usual assumption that CMC is studied from performative speech
Explored potential for hospital-based interdisciplinary care (Lancaster et al., 2015)	Phenomenological study; Schutzian lifeworld phenomenological orchestra	Hospital based MDs RNs Unlicensed personnel	Semi-structured, face to face interviews Tape-recorded and transcribed	MD-RN hierarchies still exist Knowledge and perceptions of roles contribute to the hierarchy Unlicensed personnel describe relationships with RNs as uncooperative and hierarchical Ideal CMC and CMC involves making rounds together	IPC increases effectiveness of healthcare delivery
To describe how power is commoditized and exchanged by ICU team members in daily interactions (Lingard, Espin, Evans, & Hawryluck, 2004)	Qualitative method with focus groups	ICU team members 2 urban teaching hospitals	Semi-structured interviews & focus groups	Two dominant themes: (1) The perception of ownership (2) The process of trade	Team collaboration is rooted in ownership and trade of commodities Not generalizable

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Explore if specific CMC elements contribute to nurses' CMC SAT (Manojlovich & Antonakos, 2008)	Secondary analysis, Descriptive, Survey <u>IV</u> : Elements of CMC: timeliness, openness, understanding, accuracy <u>DV</u> : CMC SAT Level of MD, JS <u>CV</u> : Race, Years in ICU, Unit type, Time spent CMC with various levels of MDs	25 ICUs, 8 hospitals in Southeast Michigan	<u>DV</u> : 1) CMC a) ICU RN-MD Questionnaire b) CMC SAT - Visual analog scale 2) Time spent in communication different level of MDs 3) JS: Single-item Likert-type 4-point scale	CMC SAT: Strong correlations: openness, understanding Moderate correlations: timeliness Weak correlation: Accuracy CMC SAT MD level: Attending + contributor; first-year resident - contributor Significant positive correlation between CMC SAT and JS	CMC SAT important for improving effective CMC Openness, understanding, accuracy most important Limitations: CMC rating scales do not capture multi-dimensions, cross-sectional rather than longitudinal, convenience sample, independent variable not defined
Characterize RN and MD CMC during urgent labor and delivery decisions (Matzke et al., 2014)	Descriptive, Observational Key Variables: TCC, Effective CMC, Ineffective CMC, Types of CMC (other directed, self-directed, generic, team centered)	Perinatal setting in an urban acute care facility Interactions audiotaped Transcription of discourse analysis used to analyze data	<u>TCC</u> : shared responsibility for tasks & problem solving; "we" <u>Effective CMC</u> : equally participating, collegial exchange r/t orders <u>Ineffective CMC</u> : discordance, interruptions, mixed messages, apologies & objections, monologues <u>Other directed</u> : telling others what to do <u>Self-directed</u> : focus on own action <u>Generic</u> : specify or imply action	TCC: MDs, 12.96%; RNs 3.64% 57% Effective CMC 43% Ineffective CMC Other Directed: 67% = commands by 52% = queries by RNs Generic: 35% MDs & RNs	Majority of RNs and MDs use other directed CMC Status differences in CMC may inhibit true collab and negatively impact patient outcomes Limitations: small sample size, recorded conversations did not capture emergent situations, no clarification or validation of perspectives from RNs and MDs about the interactions

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Characterize patterns of RN-MD CMC and agreement on patient's CP (O'Leary et al., 2010)	Descriptive, Cross-sectional, Interviews 9 Key variables: 3 variables related to characterizing CMC 6 variables related to agreement on CP	<i>n</i> = 20 patients, RN & MD for each patient. General medical inpatient setting	Responses rated for agreement on CP. Agreement = no agreement (NA), partial (PA), or complete agreement (CA)	40-50% of time MDs and RNs did not communicate regarding CP Characterizing CMC: > 65% of CMC occurred in person CP: < 60% = CA of 5 of 6 variables 11% to 42% = range for NA	Little agreement on CP; determination needs to be made regarding how to ensure complete, meaningful CMC Limitations: experience at one hospital; interview tool not a validated, reliable tool (self-created)
Explore RN and MD perceptions of effective and ineffective CMC (Robinson et al., 2010)	Focus group methodology	RNs and MDs with 5 + years of acute care acute care experience University health science center Focus group occurred in a hospital conference room. 60 minute sessions	Three focus groups, 6 participants each group Pre-focus group questionnaires provided for: a) demographic information, b) scenarios for the focus group Structured open ended questions during focus group	5 Themes of Effective CMC: 1) Clarity and precision of message that relies on verification 2) collab problem solving 3) calm and supportive demeanor under stress 4) maintenance of mutual respect 5) Authentic understanding of the unique role 3 Themes of ineffective CMC emerged: 1) Making someone less than (derision) 2) dependence on electronic systems 3) linguistic and cultural barriers	TW identified as highly valued by RNs and MDs; themes may be useful in designing learning activities Precursor to effective CMC establishment of relationship based on respect and trust RN frustration = lack of MD understanding of RN scope of practice and independent practice Limitations: viewing of the pre questionnaire, small sample size
To study RN perceptions of CMC and IP care by medical MDs (Sharma & Klocke, 2014)	Descriptive, survey; pre-test/post-test DV: perceptions of CMC and IP care, workflow, JS IV: interdisciplinary rounds	Acute hospital setting, medical unit RNs surveyed	Survey: rounding, CMC skills, work-flow, involvement and job satisfaction	Inpatient-rounding had a significantly positive effect on CMC and workflow	IPC can improve with improving IP relationships

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Describe medical mishaps according to resident MD perspective (Sutcliffe et al., 2004)	Semistructured, face-to-face interviews Inductive analysis	26 residents, 600 bed teaching hospital, US 4 dyads: Resident/Attending Resident/Community MD Resident/Resident Resident/RN	Questions: routing work environment, activities, and recent medical mishaps. Mishap = wide range of mistakes from near miss to death	70 total mishaps described 3 themes: 1) Hierarchy, power, structure 2) Lack of information 3) Mode of CMC, misinterpretation	Practitioner knowledge & CMC = main contributing factors Recommendations for briefing protocols
To measure RN and MD assessment of TW (Thomas, Sexton, & Helmreich, 2003)	Descriptive, survey ICU Management Attitudes Questionnaire (ICUMAQ)	ICUs staff in 6 hospitals	TW & collab = to communicate and make decisions with the expressed goal of satisfying the needs of the patient while respecting the unique qualities and abilities of each HCP	RN-RN = 71% high or very high MD-MD = 70% high or very high RN-MD = 33% high or very high MD-RN = 73% high or very high	Discrepant attitudes exist between RNs and MDs regarding TW
Identify barriers to effective RN-MD CMC in the LTC setting and identify strategies to overcome the barriers (Tjia et al., 2009)	Mixed Methods: Quantitative - self-administered questionnaire. Qualitative - telephone interviews Key variable: Barrier to effective CMC by telephone, Frequency of barriers to effective CMC by types	RNs at 26 Connecticut nursing homes who provided > 8 hours of direct patient care per month Semi-Structured Interviews: 10 Randomly selected 11 selectively sampled; audiotaped and transcribed	Investigator developed questionnaire adapted from another survey Categories of Questions: 1) Openness / Collab 2) Logistic Challenges 3) Professional respect/frustration 4) Language/mutual understanding 5) Nurse preparedness	26% response rate to questionnaire Top 5 barriers to RN-MD CMC: RNs hurried by MDs; no quiet place to make call; RNs felt they were bothering MD; rudeness/disrespect with interruption; language barrier 21 qualitative interviews, barriers: lack of preparedness, speaking with covering MDs not familiar with the patient, lack of trust between HCPs, no response from MD	Improved CMC depends on preparedness, responsiveness, collaborativeness, and professionalism Limitations: limited to Connecticut, did not include physicians, reliability of questionnaire

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Analyzes time RNs spend in SC with the other HCPs and RNs based on years of experience or unit worked (Tschannen et al., 2013)	Pilot study, Descriptive, Cross-Sectional, Observational Key Variables: SC, AC, CMC time with HCP, NE level, PRC, NPRC, Unit type	<i>n</i> = 12 RNs Three different units: adult ICU, general care unit, pediatric general care unit Two day shift and two night shift RNs from each unit	Modified Microsoft Office Access database through AHRQ for 11 discrete nursing activities SC = verbal exchanges AC = indirect methods NE = < 5 years or > 5 years	SC: HCT = 171.2 min (SD = 41.2) RNs = 77.04 min (SD = 36.83) SC = 171.2 min (PRC = 130.63 min; NPR = 40.52 min) HCPs = 33.47 min (SD = 31.11) UAPs = 8.49 min (SD = 18.13) MDs = 11.27 min (SD = 9.48) NE: < 5 years = 187.90 average min with HCPs > 5 years = 163.70 average min with HCPs Unit Type: No significant differences	24% of time in SC during a 12-hour shift SC with MDs only 1.5% of time for 12 hour shift Consider time in SC for interventions to improve CMC and/or CMC effectiveness Limitations: small convenience sample, subjectivity of observations and potential for the same activity to be recorded under different categories; limited to verbal CMC
Does usage of AS, CS, or DS impact perceptions of collab, QOC, and RN SAT (Van Ess Coeling & Cukr, 2000)	Posttest design with nonequivalent groups IV: Category of Norton's communicator style (AS, CS, DS), RN, MD DV: POC, Perceptions of QOC, Perceptions of RN SAT	Ambulatory and inpatient sites at medical centers, teaching hospitals, and community hospitals RN interactions while: a) Completing coursework b) Working for pay as a RN	IV: CMC style (AS, CS, DS) face-to-face or via telephone. DV: 1) POC (yes/no question) 2) QOC via five-point Likert-type scale 3) RN SAT via three-point Likert-type scale POC: active integration of the perspectives	RNs: AS > + POC***, + QOC*, + RN SAT*** Non-usage of CS > + POC*** + QOC***, + RN SAT*** Non-usage of DS > + POC*** + QOC***, + RN SAT*** MDs: Usage of AS and non-usage of a CS or DS > POC, improved QOC, and increased RN SAT***	Use of AS and avoiding CS or DS + Strategies for teaching and promoting AS and avoiding CS and DS provided Limitations: Non-random sample of graduate RN students only, other factors of collaboration not evaluated, interactions not analyzed only perceptions of interactions

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To determine the quality of the RN-MD relationship by examining the CMC and interaction between RNs and resident physician from the residents' perspective. (Weinberg et al., 2009)	Structured, open-ended questions via telephone Relational coordination Snowball sampling	Telephone interviews Questions correlated with the seven dimensions of relational COORDN: 1) Frequent of CMC 2) Timely CMC 3) Accurate CMC 4) Problem-solving CMC 5) Mutual respect 6) Shared knowledge 7) SGs	Telephone interviews, 45 minutes Telephone interviews recorded and transcribed	20 medical and surgical residents; 11 men and nine women Theme: "It Depends" Relational coordination depended on: 1) Cooperativeness of the nurse 2) Competence of the nurse	Questions ability of nurses to overcome obstacles to good CMC on their own. Individual nurses efforts may be undermined by other nurses Limitations: qualitative design, small sample, interview question variability

Notes. AC = Asynchronous Communication; AS = Attentive Style; AHRQ = Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality; CA = Complete Agreement; CC = Confirmation Communication; CMC = Communication; CP = Care plan/plan of care; CS = Contentious Style; CV = Control Variables; DC = Disconfirmation Communication; DS = Dominant Style; DV = Dependent Variable; EC = Effective Communication; HCP = Healthcare Personnel; HCT = healthcare team; IV = Independent Variable; JS = Job Satisfaction; LTC = Long Term Care; MD = Physician; min = Minutes; N = No Agreement; NCC = Nurse-Centered Communication; NE = Nurse Experience; NPRC = Non-Patient Related Communication; PA = Partial Agreement; PCC = Patient-Centered Communication; POC = Perceptions of Collaboration; PRC = Patient Related Communication; QOC = Quality of Care; RN = Registered Nurse; RS = Relationship Satisfaction; SAT = satisfaction; SC = Synchronous Communication; TCC = Team-Centered Communication; UAP = Unlicensed Assistive Personnel.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Evidence Table 3. For Patient-And-Family Centered Care

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Conceptual Underpinnings; Design	Sample & Setting	Procedures & Analysis	Results; Theoretical Integration	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Explores context of parent/nurse interactions and how social norms may counter the delivery of PFCC (Baird et al., 2015)	Grounded theory; constructivist, postmodern conceptualization	Pediatric ICU; large, urban teaching hospital	Field notes Interviews that were audio-recorded and transcribed	Themes include: (a) Explicit rules: struggling with the rules, enforcing the rules (b) Implicit rules: knowing the hospital routine, understanding care priorities, respecting the nurse as a professional	Rules that appear to maintain order or for the convenience of the staff, rather than safety are the most frustrating for parents and nurses Single site study with specific rules that may not be found in other organizations
Identify work system barriers and facilitators for FCRs (Carayon et al., 2014)	Stimulated recall methodology (Human Factors and Ergonomics)	Children's hospital in a US hospital	Families and HCT viewed video of PCRs with discussion of barriers and facilitators Survey to evaluate the stimulated recall methodology	5 categories of barriers and facilitators: (1) Tools and technologies (2) Environment (3) Person (4) Tasks (5) Organization	The information from the findings can be used to redesign patient care rounds
Explores the impact FCRs rounds related to outcomes and SAT (Cypress, 2012)	Systematic Review Adults and pediatric patients FCRs = in patients' rooms, family & patient present, patient & family perspective included in CDM	Inclusion: FP on rounds, adult, pediatric, ICUs, non-ICUs Exclusion: end-of life situations	Family member impact of FCRs: 10 + findings; 3 - findings HCP impact of FCRs: 11 + findings; 4 -findings	FCRs can facilitate a PC environment Qualitative research is needed CPGs for implementation at the local level needed	Data is limited, especially adult population No RCTs Outcome measures for studies not clearly defined

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Conceptual Underpinnings; Design	Sample & Setting	Procedures & Analysis	Results; Theoretical Integration	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Develop CPGs for family support in a PCC ICU (Davidson et al., 2007)	Clinical Practice Guideline	Inclusion: adult, pediatric, neonatal related to PCC	Recommendations made: SDM (5), family coping (5), staff stress (2), cultural support (6), spiritual support (4), FV (6), FEC (3), FP on rounds (4), FP at resuscitation (3), palliative care (5)	Patient and family participation in SDM key; reduce patient autonomy versus paternalism Recommendations should be implemented	No clear methodology for implementation of the recommendations
Identify and describe barriers to PCC (Esmaeili, 2014)	Qualitative exploratory study with thematic analysis approach	Critical care unit RNs	Semi-structured interviews, audio-taped and transcribed	Three themes: 1) Lack of common understanding of teamwork – lack of team coordination and acceptance of PCC 2) Personal Barriers – lack of motivation to provide PCC; lacking holistic view instead of task based view of role 3) Organizational Barriers – shortage of staff, time, and workload pressures	Nurses lack organizational coordination, time, motivation, and training to provided PCC Limitations: focus groups may be needed
Identify common, core elements of PFCC across disciplines (Kitson et al., 2013)	Narrative review and literature synthesis	Inclusion: English, 1990-2010, acute care setting, nursing, medicine, health policy Exclusion: social care, nursing home, residential, aged care	Three main themes: 1) Patient participation and involvement – 3 sub-themes 2) Relationship between the patient and HCPs – 4 sub-themes 3) Context of delivered care – 1 sub-theme	PFCC across disciplines does have core commonalities Need: implementation of PFCC within IPC	No critical appraisal due to wide variation in literature

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Conceptual Underpinnings; Design	Sample & Setting	Procedures & Analysis	Results; Theoretical Integration	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Identify key attributes of PFCC & provided EBP recommendations for implementation (Mastro et al., 2014)	Integrative Review	Inclusion: PCC, PFCC, FCC, patient partnerships, pediatrics Exclusion: adults	Concepts and Activities for Antecedents, PFCC structure, PFCC partnership processes, & PFCC outcomes identified	Evidence exists to support PFCC Nurse competencies should be developed to implement PFCC	Limited number of studies that inform the evidence
Identify specific and non-specific elements of PCC to facilitate IPC implementation (Sidani & Fox, 2014)	Integrative review; analysis and integration of conceptual, empirical, and clinical literature	Inclusion: adults, English, conceptual papers using models/frameworks; empirical for HCP or patients' perceptions; clinical case studies or initiative for application Exclusion: pediatrics	3 specific elements: 1) Holistic care (all domains of health), 2) Collab care (SDM), 3) Responsive care (individualization) Non-specific element of PCC: therapeutic alliance (trusting & nurturing)	Based on finding protocols can be developed to promote PCC at the local level Protocols can be based on the activities described for implementation of each of the 3 specific elements of PCC	Exclusion of grey papers; informal review of papers Applicability to different practice areas not explored
To understand alignment of principles of FCC and FCRs in practice (Subramony et al., 2014)	Ethnography	General pediatric inpatient unit; large academic medical center English speaking patients and family members Family members = caregiver present at the bedside at the time of rounds	Observation using ethnography = detailed description of naturally occurring interactions	Principles: (1) Clear and open information sharing with patients and family members (2) Respect for patients and family members (3) Participation of patients and family members (4) Collaboration with patients and family members 7 practices identified that are misaligned with FCC principles	Practice does not always integrate principles of FCC; may partly result from contextual factors of the organizational setting

Notes. CPG = clinical practice guideline; FCC = family centered care; FCR = family centered round; FEC = family environment of care; FP = family presence; FV = family visitation; HCP = health care provider; HCT = health care team; ICU = intensive care or critical care; IPC = interprofessional collaboration; PCC = patient centered care; PCR = patient care rounds; PFCC = patient-and-family centered care; RCT = randomized control trial; SAT = satisfaction; SDM = shared decision making.